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Master Thesis

Analyzing Municipal Process Data from the Social Domain: A Process Mining-Based Approach

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Department of Information and Computing Science,
Graduate School of Natural Sciences,
Faculty of Science.

First Supervisor:

Dr. Ir. Claudio di Ciccio
c.diciccio@uu.nl

Student:

Floris van Voorst tot Voorst (5990076)
f.c.vanvoorsttotvoorst@students.uu.nl

Second Supervisor:

Dr. Ir. Xixi Lu
x.lu@uu.nl

Centric Supervisor

Ron Bartels
ron.bartels@centric.eu

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Abstract

Municipalities deliver essential social services through complex processes that often suffer from inefficiencies and bottlenecks. Municipal information systems record detailed execution data on these processes. However, the data is often fragmented and noisy, making it difficult to analyze the data systematically and identify improvement opportunities.

In response to these challenges, this thesis presents a process mining-based framework for extracting process knowledge from raw municipal data in the social domain. The framework defines an end-to-end pipeline that preprocesses, transforms, and integrates fragmented municipal process data into structured XES event logs and regulatory patterns. From these, the framework systematically generates descriptive process models via process discovery techniques (reflecting actual execution behavior) and normative process models via the regulatory patterns (representing intended workflows).

By applying conformance checking and additional process diagnostics, the framework identifies deviations between actual and intended process behavior, as well as other actionable insights to potentially improve these processes. The framework is implemented and demonstrated on two municipal datasets, illustrating how the pipeline operates on real-world data and detailing the results of each step of the framework.

To ensure reproducibility, the framework's design and implementation are made publicly available, with each step documented in detail. The case study datasets and all resulting outputs of the framework, including the structured XES event logs, descriptive and normative models, and diagnostic results, are also published for transparency and future use.

Keywords: Process Mining; XES event log; Normative models; Descriptive models; Municipal Processes; Social Domain; Conformance Checking; Process Diagnostics.

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1 Introduction

Municipalities are responsible for delivering a wide range of essential social services to their residents, such as debt counseling, youth services, employment support, income assistance, housing support, and more. These services directly impact citizens' well-being and are therefore expected to be executed efficiently, in compliance with the applicable laws and regulations, and within a certain time frame. However, in practice, these municipal processes are often complex and involve multiple departments, numerous steps, and rules. This can lead to inefficiencies, where cases have a lengthy handling time, redundant approvals or other bottlenecks that delay processes. The lack of transparency in how these processes are executed in practice makes it difficult to assess where the problems occur and how to improve them.

This thesis is written in collaboration with Centric, which provides software solutions to municipalities. These software solutions generate vast amounts of raw process data, including records of every case and its corresponding actions. This raw process data could in principle provide objective insights into how a process really operates and whether it conforms to the intended workflow that is designed by the municipality. However, the raw process data is typically scattered over multiple database tables [1] [2] and often contains errors, noise, and missing values [3]. This makes harnessing the raw process data for process improvement challenging.

The motivation for this research stems from the need for more efficient municipal processes, particularly in the social domain. These processes are often critical for citizens' well-being, and the consequences of inefficient processes directly impact them, while also wasting public funds and undermining trust in municipalities. The traditional approaches for process improvements struggle to deal with the complexity and volume of the raw process data. This is where process mining offers an opportunity.

Process mining is a technique that aims to improve operational processes through the systematic use of event data. By using a combination of recorded event data and formal process models, process mining techniques can provide deep insights into actual execution flows, help identify process bottlenecks and deviations, and diagnose compliance or performance problems [4].

Process mining techniques can be divided into three types: process discovery, conformance checking, and process enhancement. Process discovery takes an event log and produces a process model without a priori information, conformance checking compares an event log with a process model for analysis and process enhancement aims to enrich and improve a process model [5]. However, several problems must be solved for process mining techniques to be effectively applied to municipal processes.

The first problem that arises is that the raw municipal process data has particular characteristics and challenges that have not been fully addressed in prior research. As mentioned before, the data

is extracted from several different database tables, thus requiring substantial preprocessing and domain understanding to create well-structured event data that serves as an input for the use of process mining techniques. Furthermore, the data quality problems that real-life event data suffers from must first be resolved, which can take a significantly long time [6]. Solving this problem will result in clean, usable, and structured event data for further analysis.

The second problem is the need to extract process knowledge from the raw municipal process data to formulate descriptive and normative process models. A descriptive model represents the actual processes within the event data, often discovered via process discovery, while a normative model represents how the process is supposed to operate according to the workflow designed by a municipality. Generating these models systematically from the structured event data is key for the applicability to derive insights and deviations.

The final problem concerns demonstrating which insights and deviations can be derived from the structured event data in combination with the descriptive and normative models. These findings could be used to support municipalities in pinpointing potential opportunities to improve the efficiency of their processes, which in turn would enhance citizens' well-being.

In summary, although municipalities have a wealth of raw process data at their disposal, there is a lack of established techniques and process knowledge to convert this raw data into structured event data and process models that could potentially provide meaningful insights. Without this process knowledge, the municipalities lack the opportunity to improve the efficiency of their processes.

1.1 Research Objective

Given the problems stated above, the research objective of this thesis is to develop a process mining-based approach to extract actionable process knowledge from raw municipal process data, in order to enable analysis of the processes and identify potential improvements in efficiency.

To achieve this objective, the following main research question is formulated:

***RQ:** How can process knowledge be extracted from raw municipal process data to enable the analysis and (potential) improvement of municipal processes in the social domain via process mining?*

The following sub-questions are formulated to answer the main research question. Each sub-question corresponds to a major phase of the process mining approach:

***SRQ1:** What are the characteristics and challenges of raw municipal process data in the social domain, and how can it be effectively processed and restructured for process mining?*

This sub-question focuses on the raw process data that is extracted from various municipal database tables. It aims to identify the different characteristics and challenges included within the raw data. These can be used to gain domain-specific process knowledge, which aids in the preprocessing, transformation, and cleaning of the raw data. The result of this sub-question will be well-structured

event data that can be used for further analysis.

***SRQ2:** How can descriptive and normative process models be systematically generated to enable the analysis of municipal processes?*

This sub-question focuses on the generation of descriptive and normative models. The descriptive models are generated using the structured event data from SRQ1 and process discovery techniques. The normative models are generated using the municipality's intended workflow for the processes. The result of this sub-question will be a way to systematically generate process models, that can be used for further analysis.

***SRQ3:** What insights and deviations can be derived from analyzing and comparing process models to support potential improvement of municipal processes?*

This sub-question focuses on the insights and deviations that can be derived from the structured event data in combination with the process models that are the results of SRQ1 and SRQ2, respectively. Using conformance checking and other techniques, insights and deviations can be extracted from the process data, enabling the potential improvement of the municipal processes.

1.2 Contributions

This thesis aims to make three original contributions to the field of process mining:

1. A reproducible framework that preprocesses and restructures raw municipal process data into structured event data suitable for process mining.
2. A systematic approach for generating descriptive and normative process models that enables comparison between actual execution behavior and intended workflows.
3. The release of real-world municipal datasets, including the raw process data, the generated structured event data, and the resulting process models, to support further research and applications within the process mining community.

Furthermore, this thesis aims to provide the municipalities with information about the insights and deviations that can be derived from the analysis of the structured event data in combination with the process models. This could potentially improve the municipal processes within the social domain.

1.3 Structure of the Thesis

The remainder of this thesis is structured as follows:

Chapter 2 provides an overview of the background literature and the relevant related work. Chapter 3 presents the data used in this study, including its origin, structure, and limitations. Chapter 4 describes the municipal process analysis framework, detailing its various steps. Chapter 5 explains the practical implementation of the framework and demonstrates its application through two case studies. Chapter 6 reports the results of the process diagnostics of the framework. Finally, Chapter 7 discusses the practical and research implications of the study's findings, reflects on its limitations, outlines directions for future research, and concludes the thesis.

1.4 Ethics and Privacy

The Ethics and Privacy Quick Scan of the Utrecht University Research Institute of Information and Computing Sciences was conducted (see Appendix A). It classified this research as low-risk with no fuller ethics review or privacy assessment required.

2 Background and Related Work

This chapter provides an overview of the background literature and the relevant related work, laying the foundation for the rest of the thesis. The chapter is structured as follows:

Section 2.1 introduces the theoretical concepts of process mining and formalizes these concepts as definitions, which form the basis on which this thesis objective is built. Section 2.2 summarizes previous related work, highlighting key studies that give context to the motivation of this thesis.

2.1 Process mining

This section provides an overview of the theoretical concepts of process mining. Process mining aims to discover, monitor, and improve processes by extracting knowledge from event logs and comparing them with process models [7]. The section introduces the concepts in an intuitive and formal way and is structured as follows:

Section 2.1.1 introduces the event log and related concepts, Section 2.1.2 introduces process models, Section 2.1.3 provides a detailed overview of the different types of process mining: process discovery, conformance checking, and process enhancement, and Section 2.1.4 introduces the XES standard, which is an XML-based format for storing and exchanging event logs.

2.1.1 Event Log

An event log is the starting point for every process mining task. It contains a record of all the executed events and each event typically possess attributes that provide descriptive details. Classical process mining literature dictates that an event must at least possess the following attributes: a case identifier (i.e. a process instance), an activity label (i.e. a well-defined step in a process), and a timestamp (i.e. the time of execution). Additionally, an event can contain other attributes in the form of resources or other data elements [8].

Event logs organize events related to the same process instance, i.e. events that share the same case identifier, into cases. The events within a case are ordered, where the ordering is most often derived from the timestamp attribute, but this is not strictly mandatory [9].

A case itself can possess case-specific attributes, which are attributes that have an identical value for all events inside of that case [10] or attributes that contain general information about the case [10]. An example is the case identifier attribute. Since each event in a case has the same value for the case identifier attribute, the case itself also possesses this attribute.

Since the case has an ordering of events, a case can be represented by a sequence of events. Each of these events in the sequence has an activity label attribute, which implies that a case can also be represented by a sequence of activity labels. This sequence of activity labels is called a trace [11]. Different cases within an event log can have the same sequence of activity labels, therefore an event log can be abstracted to a multiset of traces. The multiset of traces indicates how many times the

same trace appears inside of an event log [12].

	Case Identifier	Activity Label	Timestamp	Employee	Cost
e_1	111	Register Request	2025-01-01 08:15:00	John	100
e_2	111	Approve Request	2025-01-01 09:30:00	Jane	150
e_3	222	Register Request	2025-01-02 14:45:00	Sarah	100
e_4	222	Reject Request	2025-01-02 15:30:00	Daniel	-
e_5	333	Register Request	2025-01-02 16:20:00	Bryan	100
e_6	111	Send Confirmation	2025-01-02 16:50:00	Mark	50
e_7	444	Register Request	2025-01-03 09:10:00	Alice	100
e_8	444	Approve Request	2025-01-03 09:55:00	Bob	150
e_9	444	Send Confirmation	2025-01-03 10:30:00	Carol	50
e_{10}	333	Approve Request	2025-01-03 13:00:00	Clyde	150
e_{11}	333	Archive Request	2025-01-03 14:30:00	Peter	30
e_{12}	555	Register Request	2025-01-04 08:05:00	Dave	100
e_{13}	555	Reject Request	2025-01-04 09:00:00	Emily	-
e_{14}	666	Register Request	2025-01-05 10:15:00	Fred	100
e_{15}	666	Approve Request	2025-01-05 12:00:00	Grace	150
e_{16}	666	Archive Request	2025-01-06 09:20:00	Henry	30
e_{17}	777	Register Request	2025-01-06 11:00:00	Irene	100
e_{18}	777	Approve Request	2025-01-07 10:45:00	Jack	150
e_{19}	777	Send Confirmation	2025-01-07 15:30:00	Kelly	50
e_{20}	777	Archive Request	2025-01-08 08:55:00	Liam	30

Table 2.1: Illustrative example of an event log.

As a motivating example, consider the event log in Table 2.1. Each row represents a single event, denoted on the far-left as e_i and there are 20 events in total. The first three columns contain the mandatory event attributes *Case Identifier*, *Activity Label*, and *Timestamp*, while the other columns contain the additional attributes, such as the employee who executed the event (*Resource*) and how much the event costs (*Data element*).

The event log contains seven different cases, since there are seven different unique values for the case identifier attribute. Each case is listed below with their ordered sequence of events:

1. Case 111 contains the event sequence: $\langle e_1, e_2, e_6 \rangle$
2. Case 222 contains the event sequence: $\langle e_3, e_4 \rangle$
3. Case 333 contains the event sequence: $\langle e_5, e_{10}, e_{11} \rangle$
4. Case 444 contains the event sequence: $\langle e_7, e_8, e_9 \rangle$
5. Case 555 contains the event sequence: $\langle e_{12}, e_{13} \rangle$
6. Case 666 contains the event sequence: $\langle e_{14}, e_{15}, e_{16} \rangle$
7. Case 777 contains the event sequence: $\langle e_{17}, e_{18}, e_{19}, e_{20} \rangle$

The event log can be abstracted to the following multiset of traces, obtained by mapping each event sequence to the corresponding sequence of activity labels (traces):

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} \langle \text{Register Request, Approve Request, Send Confirmation} \rangle^2, \\ \langle \text{Register Request, Reject Request} \rangle^2, \\ \langle \text{Register Request, Approve Request, Archive Request} \rangle^2, \\ \langle \text{Register Request, Approve Request, Send Confirmation, Archive Request} \rangle^1 \end{array} \right]$$

This shows that even though the event log has seven distinct cases, there are only four trace variants, underlining how the discoverable behavior of a process often collapses into a compact set of recurring patterns. In real-life scenarios, its often the case that a handful of trace variants cover a large share of the cases [11].

The different concepts of events, attributes, event logs, cases, and traces are now introduced intuitively. This next part will dive deeper into these concepts from a formal standpoint.

The first definition is that of an event, which is defined as:

Definition 1 (Event).

Let $U_e \ni e$ be a finite, non-empty set of symbols. e is an event and U_e is the universe of events. \triangleleft

Each event possess attributes that provide descriptive details, these are defined as:

Definition 2 (Event attribute).

Let \mathcal{A} be a finite, non-empty set of attribute names. For every $attr \in \mathcal{A}$ there is a universe U_{attr} of admissible values. The attribute function for $attr$ is a partial map:

$$attr: U_e \rightarrow U_{attr}$$

which maps events to values in U_{attr} . The value mapped by $attr$ to an event e is indicated by using the dot notation: $e.attr$. \triangleleft

The attribute function is a partial mapping, which allows for a particular attribute to be missing for a given event. This is shown in Table 2.1, where the cost column is empty for row e_4 or e_{13} , which means that for those particular events this attribute is missing.

As mentioned before, in the classical process mining literature there are certain attributes that are mandatory for each event. This is addressed in the following postulate:

Postulate 2.1 (Mandatory event attributes).

The following attributes are total on the universe of events U_e :

1. $iid: U_e \rightarrow U_{iid}$, the **case identifier**;
2. $act: U_e \rightarrow U_{act}$, the **activity label**;
3. $tms: U_e \rightarrow \mathbb{N}_{>0}$, the **timestamp**.

U_{iid} and U_{act} are finite, non-empty universes, and $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ denotes the set of positive integers. All other attributes may remain partial as in Def. 2. \triangleleft

Note that the case identifier is a total surjective function, meaning that an event has exactly one case identifier, and every case identifier appears in at least one event.

Given the definitions of events, the event log can be defined as:

Definition 3 (Event log).

Given the universe of events U_e (Def. 1), let $\preceq \subseteq U_e \times U_e$ be a total-order relation defined over U_e . The pair $L = (U_e, \preceq)$ is called an event log. \triangleleft

It is assumed that the total order of events can be reconstructed based on the timestamps of the events, which is addressed with the following postulate:

Postulate 3.1 (Timestamp as an monotonic order).

Given an event log $L = (U_e, \preceq)$ (Def. 3), The total timestamp event attribute:

$$tms: U_e \rightarrow \mathbb{N}_{>0} \quad (\text{Post. 2.1})$$

is a monotonic order, i.e., for all $e, e' \in U_e$ with $e \neq e'$ follows:

$$e \preceq e' \implies e.tms \leq e'.tms.$$

\triangleleft

Looking at the events e_1 and e_4 in the event log of Table 2.1, it can be deduced from the order relation based on the timestamps that e_1 precedes e_4 , i.e. $e_1 \preceq e_4$. This holds true for any generic pair of events selected from the event log.

A case inside of an event log can be defined as:

Definition 4 (Case).

Given an event log $L = (U_e, \preceq)$ (Def. 3) and given the total / surjective case-identifier event attribute: $iid: U_e \rightarrow U_{iid}$ (Post. 2.1).

For every identifier $iid \in U_{iid}$, a case σ defined by iid over L is a finite sequence

$$\sigma_{iid} := \langle e_{iid,1}, \dots, e_{iid,n} \rangle, \quad \text{where } n \in \mathbb{N}_{>0},$$

such that:

1. $e_{iid,\iota}.iid = iid$ for every $1 \leq \iota \leq n$;
2. $e_{iid,i} \preceq_{\sigma_{iid}} e_{iid,j}$ for every $i \leq j \leq n$,

where $\preceq_{\sigma_{iid}}$ is a total order restricting the log order \preceq over the events in σ_{iid} .

Since $\preceq_{\sigma_{iid}} \subseteq \preceq$ and \preceq is a total order that is monotonic with respect to the timestamp event attribute (Post. 3.1), it follows that for all events $e, e' \in \sigma_{iid}$:

$$e \preceq_{\sigma_{iid}} e' \implies e.tms \leq e'.tms.$$

Let $C(L)$ be the set of cases contained in an event log L :

$$C(L) := \{\sigma_\iota \mid \iota \in U_{iid}\},$$

which is finite, non-empty, and contains exactly one case for every identifier in U_{iid} . \triangleleft

In the motivating example, the event log contained seven different cases, one case for every unique case-identifier attribute value. Case *III* contained the ordered event sequence $\langle e_1, e_2, e_6 \rangle$, since $e_1.iid = e_2.iid = e_6.iid = 111$.

Each case possess case-specific attributes, which are attributes that have an identical value for all events inside of that case or attributes that contain general information about the case. These case attributes are defined as:

Definition 5 (Case attribute).

Let \mathcal{A} be a finite, non-empty set of attribute names. For every $attr \in \mathcal{A}$ there is a universe U_{attr} of admissible values. The attribute function for $attr$ is a partial map:

$$attr: C(L) \rightarrow U_{attr}$$

which maps cases to values in U_{attr} . The value mapped by $attr$ to a case σ is indicated by using the dot notation: $\sigma.attr$. ◁

Since each case contains only events with the same case-identifier value, that shared case-identifier becomes a mandatory attribute of the case itself. This is formalized in the following postulate:

Postulate 5.1 (Mandatory case attributes).

The following attributes are total on the set of cases $C(L)$:

1. $iid: C(L) \rightarrow U_{iid}$, the **case identifier**;
- U_{iid} , is a finite, non-empty universe. All other attributes may remain partial as in Def. 5. ◁

Each case can be mapped to a sequence of activity labels, i.e. a trace, which is defined as:

Definition 6 (Trace).

Given a case $\sigma_i \in C(L)$ of the event log L , with sequence $\langle e_{i,1}, \dots, e_{i,n} \rangle$ (Def. 4), and given the total activity-label event attribute $act: U_e \rightarrow U_{act}$ (Post. 2.1).

The trace induced by σ_i is the sequence

$$t(\sigma_i) := \langle e_{i,1}.act, \dots, e_{i,n}.act \rangle \in U_{act}^*$$

i.e. the ordered list of activity labels obtained by applying act to each event of the case. ◁

In the motivating example, the event log was abstracted as a multiset of traces. A multiset is defined as:

Definition 7 (Multiset).

Let X be a set. A multiset over X is a function $B: X \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$, where $B(x)$ gives the multiplicity of $x \in X$. The set of all finite multisets over X is denoted by $\mathbb{B}(X)$. ◁

And the multiset of traces as an abstraction of the event log can be defined as:

Definition 8 (Multiset of traces).

Given an event log $L = (U_e, \preceq)$ (Def. 3):

1. There exists a finite, non-empty set of cases

$$C(L) := \{\sigma_i \mid i \in U_{iid}\} \quad (\text{Def. 4}).$$

2. For every case $\sigma_i \in C(L)$ there is a trace $t(\sigma_i)$, denoting an ordered list of activity labels of the case (Def. 6).

Hence, an event log can be abstracted to a multiset of traces:

$$\text{Traces}(L) := [t(\sigma_i) \mid \sigma_i \in C(L)],$$

where multiplicities reflect how many distinct cases yield the same trace. ◁

This subsection introduced the concepts of events, attributes, event logs, cases, and traces in both intuitive and formal terms, illustrated by a motivating example. The next subsection will introduce the different process models that are used in process mining.

2.1.2 Process Models

A process model aims to describe the behavior of a process by defining the activities involved, the order in which they are executed and their control-flow dependencies [2]. Process models play a fundamental role in process mining, as they are used in combination with event logs for process discovery, conformance checking, and process enhancement techniques. These techniques will be discussed in Section 2.1.3.

Several process modeling notations exist, each offering distinct advantages and suited for different purposes. Commonly used in process mining are the Directly-Follows Graphs (DFG), Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN), Process Tree and Petri Net [4].

A DFG is a directed graph whose nodes represent activities, and whose edges indicate directly-follows relationships between them. Despite its minimalist semantics, it effectively captures the main routing possibilities of a process and offers great initial insights [13]. However, DFGs tend to under-fit, often producing models that allow behavior, such as loops, that are not supported by the observed data [14].

A BPMN is a graphical notation designed to represent the control flow of business processes in a way that is both human-readable and executable. It includes constructs for activities, events, and gateways. Gateways express control flow patterns such as exclusive choice (XOR) and concurrent execution (AND). The sequence flow is represented by arrows. The notation is especially well-suited for modeling complex, real-world processes while remaining understandable and human-readable [15].

A Petri Net is a directed bipartite graph with two node types, places (represented by circles) and transitions (represented as rectangles), which are connected via directed arcs. A Workflow Net is a special type of Petri Net designed to model complete processes. It has one unique start place (source), one unique end place (sink), and ensures that every transition and place contributes to a valid process execution from start to finish [16].

A Process Tree organizes behavior in a block-structured hierarchy. Inner nodes represent operators such as sequence, exclusive choice, parallelism, or loops, while leaves correspond to activities [17].

As a motivating example, consider the simplified process shown in Table 2.2.

ID	Activity Label	Preceding Activity/Activities
S1	Submit Request	–
S2	Assessment	S1
S3	Background Check	S2
S4	Reference Check	S2
S5	Credit Check	S2
S6	Evaluation	S3, S4, S5
S7	Accept Support Plan	S6
S8	Reject Support Plan	S6
S9	Inform Client	S7, S8

Table 2.2: Illustrative example of a process.

The process begins when a citizen submits a request for support. After an initial assessment, three parallel checks are conducted: a background check, a reference check, and a credit check. Once all checks are completed, the case is evaluated. Based on this evaluation, the request is either accepted or rejected. In both cases, the process concludes by informing the client.

In Fig. 2.1, the four different representations of this process model are shown, using a Directly-Follows Graph (DFG), Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN), Workflow Net (WF-net), and Process Tree.

Although each model in Fig. 2.1 describes the same intended behavior, they differ significantly in structure, abstraction, and expressive power. The DFG provides a fast and scalable overview by capturing directly-follows relations between activities. However, it lacks formal semantics for concurrency and does not distinguish between parallel execution and interleaving. As a result, the DFG may allow infinitely many execution paths, including loops, that were never in the actual process [4].

The BPMN introduces explicit gateways to model control-flow constructs such as exclusive choice and parallel execution. Its notation supports both control-flow and communication aspects, making it human-readable.

The Process Tree clearly reflects the structured nature of the process, capturing the sequence of phases and the parallel execution of the checks using dedicated operators. However, this model representation is rarely presented to end-users, but more often used by process mining algorithms internally [4].

The Workflow Net models the same process using places and transitions, providing a precise representation of concurrency and decision points. Compared to the other models, it offers the most detailed execution semantics and serves as a solid basis for formal analysis, such as verifying soundness and reachability [18].

(a) DFG Representation.

(b) BPMN Representation.

(c) Workflow Net Representation.

(d) Process Tree Representation.

Figure 2.1: Alternative representations of process models based on the example process.

The different process models are now introduced intuitively. This next part will introduce the different process models from a formal standpoint.

A Directly-Follows Graph (DFG) is defined as:

Definition 9 (Directly-Follows Graph).

A Directly-Follows Graph is a directed graph $DFG = (A, F)$, where:

- A is a finite set of activities,
- $F \subseteq A \times A$ is the directly-follows relation, indicating which activity can follow which.

Additionally, two special symbols are used:

- $\blacktriangleright \notin A$ denotes the start of the process.
- $\blacksquare \notin A$ denotes the end of the process.

◁

The DFG shown in Fig. 2.1b includes both the start symbol \blacktriangleright and end symbol \blacksquare to indicate possible entry and exit points of the process. Note that a DFG is not restricted to a single start or end activity; multiple activities may be connected to start and end to reflect multiple possible entry and exit points.

A Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) is defined as:

Definition 10 (Business Process Model and Notation).

A Business Process Model and Notation is a tuple

$$BPMN = (N, A, G, E, F, L, \ell)$$

where:

- N is a finite set of nodes (activities, events, gateways).
- $A \subseteq N$ are activities.
- $G \subseteq N$ are gateways (e.g., XOR, AND).
- $E \subseteq N$ are start/end events.
- $F \subseteq N \times N$ is the sequence flow.
- $L = \Sigma$, where Σ is an alphabet.
- $\ell : A \rightarrow L$ is the labeling function of activities.

◁

In Fig. 2.1a, the BPMN model includes a start and end event, as well as two types of gateways: an exclusive choice gateway (\times) to model decisions, and a parallel gateway ($+$) to represent concurrent execution. The semantics of these gateways depend on their position in the model: a gateway with multiple outgoing edges is a split, while one with multiple incoming edges functions is a join.

A Petri Net is defined as:

Definition 11 (Petri Net).

A place/transition net (henceforth, P/T net) is a bipartite graph (P, T, F) , where P (the finite set of “places”) and T (the finite set of “transitions”) constitute the nodes ($P \cap T = \emptyset$), and the flow relation $F \subseteq (P \times T \uplus T \times P)$ defines the edges.

Let Σ be an alphabet, and $\tau \notin \Sigma$ a silent action.

A Petri Net is a labeled P/T net $\mathcal{PN} = (P, T, F, A, \ell)$ where $A = \Sigma \uplus \{\tau\}$ is the set of labels of a Petri Net, and $\ell: T \rightarrow A$ is the labeling function of transitions. \triangleleft

As mentioned before, the Workflow Net is a special type of petri net, which is defined as:

Definition 12 (Workflow Net).

A Workflow Net $\mathcal{WN} = (P, T, F, A, \ell)$ is a Petri Net such that:

1. There is a unique place (“initial place”, $\blacktriangleright \in P$) such that its preset is empty;
2. There is a unique place (“output place”, $\blacksquare \in P$) such that its postset is empty;
3. Every place $p \in P$ and transition $t \in T$ is on a path of the underlying graph from \blacktriangleright to \blacksquare .

\triangleleft

In Fig. 2.1c, the Workflow Net has one source and one sink place. The unique source place and sink place clearly define the start and end of the process. Each activity is represented as a labeled transition, and it is structured such that every place and transition lies on a path from the initial place to the final place.

A Process Tree is defined as:

Definition 13 (Process Tree).

Let A be a finite set of activity labels, and let $\tau \notin A$ denote a silent activity. A process tree P_t over A is a rooted, ordered tree where:

- Each **leaf node** is labeled with an activity $a \in A \cup \{\tau\}$.
- Each **internal node** is labeled with an operator $\oplus \in \{\rightarrow, \times, \wedge, \cup\}$ and has one or more sub-trees.
- The tree is defined inductively: each sub-tree of a node is itself a process tree.

The semantics of a process tree are recursively determined by the operators and the structure of the tree. \triangleleft

In Fig. 2.1d, the Process Tree models the process by recursively composing control-flow operators and activities. Each leaf node represents an activity, while internal nodes apply operators such as sequence (\rightarrow), exclusive choice (\times), and parallelism (\wedge) to their respective sub-trees. The three checks are grouped under a parallel operator to indicate concurrent execution, while the choice between approval and rejection is captured using an exclusive choice operator.

This subsection introduced the different process models in both an intuitive and formal way, illustrated by a motivating example. The next subsection will cover the different types of process mining.

2.1.3 Types of Process Mining

After introducing the event log and the different ways to represent process models, this subsection focuses on the application of these concepts in combination with process mining techniques. Process mining techniques can be divided into three primary types. A schematic overview is shown in Table 2.3 in terms of input and output.

Type	Input	Output
Process discovery	Event log	Process model
Conformance checking	Event log + process model	Diagnostics
Process enhancement	Event log + process model	Improved / extended model

Table 2.3: Comparison of the three primary process-mining paradigms

Process discovery takes an event log and discovers a process model, which describes the observed behavior of the event log. Conformance checking compares an existing process model with an event log and to quantify the compliance of the event log behavior within the process model. Process enhancement aims to extend and improve the process model using the information in the event log [5]. In the remainder of this subsection, each type is discussed in more detail, along with the techniques commonly used for each type.

Process discovery algorithms aim to automatically construct a process model that reflects the observed behavior in the event log, without using a-priori knowledge of the underlying process [5]. However, this task is non-trivial due to several challenges. First, event data is often incomplete and may only capture a subset of the possible behavior [11]. Second, the presence of infrequent behavior, which are often traces that deviate from the mainstream behavior, raise the question whether such behavior should be reflected in the resulting model [4].

A discovered process model must accurately reflect the dominant behavior in the event log, while also allowing behavior that is likely to belong to the process which is not in the log. At the same time, it should not allow overly permissive behavior that was never intended and it should be as simple as possible. This trade-off is assessed using four quality properties [19]:

- **Fitness:** how well the model reproduces the log.
- **Precision:** how much extra behavior the model allows.
- **Generalization:** the model's ability to allow unseen but likely behavior.
- **Simplicity:** preference for smaller, comprehensible models.

Table 2.4 shows an overview of different process discovery algorithms.

Algorithm	Description
α Miner [20]	Identifies causal relations based on directly-follows patterns. Suitable for structured logs but fails with noise, duplicate tasks, and non-free-choice constructs.
Heuristic Miner [21]	Builds models using frequency-based heuristics. It can deal with noise and exceptions by filtering out infrequent behavior.
Inductive Miner [22]	Recursively detects patterns using directly-follows graphs to build block-structured and sound models.
Genetic Miner [23]	Applies evolutionary search to evolve models over generations. Robust to noise and unstructured behavior but computationally expensive.

Table 2.4: Overview of commonly used process discovery algorithms.

In conformance checking, the behavior of a process model and the behavior recorded in an event log are compared to find commonalities and discrepancies. The conformance checking techniques provide the mechanics to relate the modeled and observed behavior [24].

Standard techniques include [8]:

1. **Footprint-based comparison:** Creates an abstraction of the behavior in the log and an abstraction of the behavior allowed by the model. These abstractions are footprint matrices, which show causal dependencies between activities. Comparing these matrices shows where the event log and model disagree.
2. **Token-replay:** replays each trace from the event log on the Petri Net of the process, counting missing / remaining tokens.
3. **Alignments:** computes optimal alignments that minimize a cost function. Offers the most fine-grained deviation information but is computationally heavier.

A process model should be precise, allowing only legitimate behavior. At the same time, it must reproduce observed executions and potentially restrict those that lead to poor performance. Process enhancement techniques aim to refine models to better meet these goals by incorporating insights from the event log [25].

There are two types of process enhancement:

1. Process extension aims to enrich the models, which often only define the control-flow, by using additional perspectives such as data, resource and time information. The resulting model should have an increased level of precision.
2. Process improvement alters the control-flow itself so that the model better reflects reality and permits only those executions that are valid and desirable from a domain viewpoint [25].

This subsection provided an overview of the different types of process mining and the techniques that are commonly used. The next subsection will introduce the XES standard.

2.1.4 XES Standard

The eXtensible Event Stream (XES) Standard permits data to be transferred from the location where it was generated to the location where it can be stored and analyzed. The XES standard is an XML-based format and regulates the syntax and the semantics of the data [26].

The model contains the log, trace and event elements. A log has one or more traces and each trace holds an ordered list of events. Every element may have any number of attributes, and an attribute can be of seven different types. Additionally, the XES contains classifiers and extensions. See Fig. 2.2 for the XES model representation.

A classifier assigns to each event an identity, which makes it comparable to others. An event classifier can be defined by one or more attributes. An example of such an identity is the descriptive name of the event. An extension defines a set of attributes for every type of element, which provides a point of reference for interpreting these attributes. Thus, extensions are primarily a way to attach semantics to the attributes of elements [27].

The concept extension, as an example, stores a generally understood name for any element. For logs, the name attribute may store the name of the process, for traces the name attribute may store the case ID, and for events the name attribute may store the executed activity.

There are several other extensions, such as:

1. The Time extension, which captures when each event occurred.
2. The Lifecycle extension, which records each event's stage (e.g., start, complete).
3. The Organizational extension, which identifies who executed each event.

In short, the XES standard provides a clear and consistent way to package and share event data, capturing both syntax and semantics through its elements, classifiers, and extensions.

In this section, the foundational elements of process mining have been presented, including event logs, process models, the different types of process mining, and the XES standard. These concepts provide the theoretical basis necessary for understanding and applying process mining techniques, on which this thesis's objective is built. The following section will summarize the previous related work.

Figure 2.2: Schematic representation of the XES meta-model [26].

2.2 Related Work

This section summarizes prior work on transforming raw data into structured event logs, deriving process models, and analyzing processes to identify improvements, with a focus on studies that use comparable approaches or municipal data.

The BPI Challenge 2015 provided real-life XES event logs of the building-permit application process from five Dutch municipalities [28]. These XES event logs contain information about the different activities of the process, the case identifiers, timestamps, as well as information about the resources and costs.

Various studies have been performed on these municipal datasets, sharing the same goal of analyzing the process behavior captured in the XES event logs to uncover insights, bottlenecks, and deviations. Teinmaa et al. [29], Martin et al. [30], and Dixit et al. [31] mainly focus on multi-perspective diagnostics, including organizational, temporal, and control-flow perspectives. Van der Ham [32] focuses on cross-municipality benchmarking to identify outliers and improvement opportunities. Tools employed in these studies include ProM and Disco, which support log exploration and process discovery through algorithms such as the Heuristics Miner and the Inductive Miner.

The key difference between these studies and this thesis's objective is that they start from pre-engineered XES event logs and do not use raw process data from municipal databases. Additionally, their data does not include explicit information about the intended workflows of the processes within the municipalities, thus a normative model cannot be derived. Their focus is on descriptive model discovery and gaining insights via process diagnostics. In contrast, this thesis aims to design an end-to-end framework that preprocesses, cleans, and transforms raw process data into structured XES event logs and systematically derives both a normative and a descriptive model from the data to enable the process diagnostics of the municipal processes.

Mannhardt and Blinde performed a study on the trajectories of patients in a Dutch hospital, from admission until discharge [33]. They used process mining techniques to analyze these trajectories to gain insights and validate compliance with medical guidelines. The data for the different patient trajectories were extracted from multiple clinical databases and transformed into an anonymized XES event log. Descriptive models were discovered with the Inductive Miner, while normative models were constructed from clinical guidelines and domain knowledge. Process diagnostics were then applied to the event log and models to gain insights into the process.

Although this study focuses on a different domain, it follows an approach similar to the objective of this thesis: extracting raw data, constructing an XES event log, and building both descriptive and normative models to enable process diagnostics. However, its normative models are hand-crafted from domain knowledge, whereas this thesis aims to generate them in a systematic and reproducible manner directly from process data and documentation. In addition, the paper does not document the transformation of the extracted data into an XES event log.

Buijs proposes the Evolutionary Tree Miner (ETM), which is a genetic discovery algorithm [34]. An extension of the algorithm discovers a descriptive model while preserving similarity to a given normative model. This algorithm is evaluated with a case study on municipal data from the CoSeLoG project, which provides the BPM configured process as the normative model, and an XES event log. The case study aims to compare the described behavior of the normative model with the observed behavior in the log.

Even though this case study explicitly aims at comparing normative and descriptive behavior, it uses both a pre-engineered XES event log and a normative model that is pre configured. It does not address constructing the event log or generating a normative model systematically from raw municipal process data, which is, as mentioned before, a critical part of the objective of this thesis.

Table 2.5 provides a summary of the studies discussed in this section, including their starting points, normative model usage, aims, and the key differences with this thesis’s objective.

Study	Starting point	Normative model	Aim	Key differences
BPI’15 analyses [29, 30, 31, 32]	Pre-engineered XES event logs.	×	Descriptive discovery & multi-perspective analysis.	No raw process data to structured XES event log; No normative model.
Mannhardt & Blinde [33]	Raw clinical process data.	✓ Hand-crafted from clinical guidelines and domain knowledge.	Validate compliance and diagnostics.	Normative model not systematic; Raw data to XES not fully documented; non-municipal domain.
Buijs [34]	Pre-engineered XES event log.	✓ BPM configured process.	Case study to evaluate the ETM discovery algorithm with the normative model.	No raw process data to structured XES event log; Normative model pre configured.
This thesis	Raw municipal process data.	✓ Systematically generated from process data and documentation.	End-to-end framework from raw process data to process diagnostics.	-

Table 2.5: Summary of the related work.

This chapter provided an overview of the relevant background literature, including the event log, process models, the different types of process mining, and the XES standard. Additionally, the chapter provided an overview of the related work, their approaches, and the differences with the objective of this thesis. The next chapter provides a detailed description of the raw municipal process data.

3 Data

This chapter provides a detailed description of the raw municipal process data that is used in this thesis. The chapter is structured as follows:

Section 3.1 details where the data comes from and who provides it. Section 3.2 presents the database schema and explains the relationships among its core tables. Section 3.3 defines the process identifier used to partition the data into distinct processes. Section 3.4 discusses the dataset's limitations. Section 3.5 discusses the privacy and data-protection measures.

3.1 Data Origin

The raw process data used in this thesis was provided by Centric, a company that provides various kinds of software solutions to municipalities. These systems handle the full life cycle of the requests, recording all intermediate steps and tasks as database entries. This data can be extracted in collaboration with municipalities that are connected with Centric.

This thesis focuses on the various processes within the social domain of municipalities, as these processes directly affect their citizens' well-being. In Centric's system, each municipality can configure its own workflows for its various processes, so there is no single standard execution path and a process can be executed differently across municipalities. The raw process data includes both the raw event data and the corresponding predefined workflow configurations.

This section detailed where the data comes from and who provides it. The next section presents the database schema and explains the relationships between its core tables.

3.2 Data Overview

Figure 3.1 shows a simplified entity-relationship diagram of the database schema, where only the database tables and attributes are shown that are relevant for the process mining analysis. This database structure is similar across all municipalities that are connected to Centric and contains the information about the various process instances and events, as well as the predefined workflow configurations. This section describes each table's purpose, key attributes, and relationships and is structured as follows:

Section 3.2.1 describes the table containing the process instances information; Section 3.2.2 describes the table containing the event information; Section 3.2.3, Section 3.2.4, and Section 3.2.5 describe the tables containing the law, category, and subcategory information; Section 3.2.6, Section 3.2.7, Section 3.2.8, and Section 3.2.9 describe the tables containing reference information; and Section 3.2.10 describes the table containing the predefined workflow configurations.

Figure 3.1: Simplified entity–relationship diagram of the database schema.

3.2.1 Process Status

The Process Status table records the current state of every process instance, capturing key data such as the unique identifier of the case, the start and end timestamps, and the responsible team and employee. All other fields are foreign keys references to related tables.

Table 3.1 outlines each field's attribute name, data type, description, and relational links.

Attribute	Type	Description	Relation
CaseId	INT	The unique identifier of a process instance.	PK
StartDate	DATETIME	The starting date of the process instance.	-
EndDate	DATETIME	The ending date of the process instance.	-
LawId	INT	The unique identifier of the process law.	FK → ProcessLaws
ProcessCategory	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the process category.	FK → ProcessCategories
ProcessSubCategory	INT	The unique identifier of the process sub category.	FK → ProcessSubCategories
TeamId	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the responsible team.	-
EmployeeId	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the responsible employee.	-
ExecutionState	INT	The execution status of the process instance.	FK → ExecutionReference
SuspensionType	INT	The type of the suspension of the process instance.	FK → SuspensionReference
ResultType	VARCHAR2	The type of the result of the process instance.	FK → ResultReference

Table 3.1: Attribute information of the Process Status Table

Several attributes in Table 3.1 are mandatory for every process instance (case) in the dataset and are essential for identifying and characterizing cases within a municipality. The CaseId attribute corresponds to the case identifier (*iid*) which is already a mandatory attribute for a case (Post. 5.1).

The following postulate formalizes the remaining domain-specific mandatory case attributes:

Postulate 5.2 (Domain-specific mandatory case attributes).

In addition to the mandatory case attributes defined in Post. 5.1, the following domain-specific attributes are total on the set of cases $C(L)$ (Def. 4):

1. *StartDate*: $C(L) \rightarrow U_{StartDate}$, the **starting date** of the case;
2. *LawId*: $C(L) \rightarrow U_{LawId}$, the **law identifier**;
3. *ProcessCategory*: $C(L) \rightarrow U_{ProcessCategory}$, the **process category**;
4. *ProcessSubCategory*: $C(L) \rightarrow U_{ProcessSubCategory}$, the **process subcategory**;
5. *ExecutionState*: $C(L) \rightarrow U_{ExecutionState}$, the **execution state**.

$U_{StartDate}$, U_{LawId} , $U_{ProcessCategory}$, $U_{ProcessSubCategory}$, and $U_{ExecutionState}$ are finite, non-empty universes. All other attributes may remain partial as in Def. 5.

◁

3.2.2 Process History

The Process History table records the history handling of each process instance, detailing the various process stages (events) that occurred during the execution of the process instance. It captures the key data, such as the unique identifier of the stage, the start and end timestamps, and the responsible team and employee. All other fields are foreign keys references to related tables.

Table 3.2 outlines each field's attribute name, data type, description, and relational links.

Attribute	Type	Description	Relation
HistoryId	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the stage.	PK
CaseId	INT	The unique identifier of the process instance.	FK → ProcessStatus
StartDate	DATETIME	The starting date of the stage.	—
EndDate	DATETIME	The ending date of the stage.	—
LawId	INT	The unique identifier of the process law.	FK → ProcessLaws
ProcessCategory	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the process category.	FK → ProcessCategories
ProcessSubCategory	INT	The unique identifier of the process sub category.	FK → ProcessSubCategories
ProcessStage	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the process stage.	FK → ProcessStages
TeamId	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the responsible team.	—
EmployeeId	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the responsible employee.	—
ResultType	VARCHAR2	The type of the result of the stage.	FK → ResultReference

Table 3.2: Attribute information of the Process History Table

Several attributes in Table 3.2 are mandatory for every event in the dataset and are essential for linking events to their respective process instances and characterizing the execution of the stages within a municipality. The CaseId attribute corresponds to the case identifier (*iid*), the ProcessStage attribute corresponds to the activity label (*act*), and the EndDate attribute corresponds to the timestamp (*tms*), which were already mandatory attributes for an event (Post. 2.1).

The following postulate formalizes the remaining domain-specific mandatory event attributes:

Postulate 2.2 (Domain-specific mandatory event attributes).

In addition to the mandatory case attributes defined in Post. 2.1, the following domain-specific attributes are total on the universe of events U_e (Def. 1):

1. *StartDate*: $U_e \rightarrow U_{StartDate}$, the **starting date** of the event;
2. *LawId*: $U_e \rightarrow U_{LawId}$, the **law identifier**;
3. *ProcessCategory*: $U_e \rightarrow U_{ProcessCategory}$, the **process category**;
4. *ProcessSubCategory*: $U_e \rightarrow U_{ProcessSubCategory}$, the **process subcategory**.

$U_{StartDate}$, U_{LawId} , $U_{ProcessCategory}$, and $U_{ProcessSubCategory}$ are finite, non-empty universes. All other attributes may remain partial as in Def. 2. ◁

3.2.3 Process Laws

The Process Law table contains all the different laws that can be applied by a municipality. It is a reference table that has unique identifiers for the different process laws and their description.

Table 3.3 outlines each field's attribute name, data type, description, and relational links.

Attribute	Type	Description	Relation
LawId	INT	The unique identifier of the process law.	PK
LawDescription	VARCHAR2	The description of the process law.	-

Table 3.3: Attribute information of the Process Laws Table

3.2.4 Process Categories

The Process Categories table contains all the different categories of processes that are associated with a specific law. It is a reference table that has unique identifiers for the different process categories and their description. These categories help to distinguish and classify the different applications of a law.

Table 3.4 outlines each field's attribute name, data type, description, and relational links.

Attribute	Type	Description	Relation
LawId	INT	The unique identifier of the process law.	FK → ProcessLaws
ProcessCategory	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the process category.	PK
CategoryDescription	VARCHAR2	The description of the process category.	-

Table 3.4: Attribute information of the Process Categories Table

3.2.5 Process Sub Categories

The Process Sub Categories table contains all the different subcategories of processes within a category. It is a reference table that has unique identifiers for the different process subcategories and their description. These subcategories help to distinguish and classify the different applications of a category within a specific law.

Table 3.5 outlines each field's attribute name, data type, description, and relational links.

Attribute	Type	Description	Relation
ProcessSubCategory	INT	The unique identifier of the process sub category.	PK
SubCategoryDescription	VARCHAR2	The description of the process sub category.	-

Table 3.5: Attribute information of the Process Sub Categories Table

3.2.6 Process Stages

The Process Stages table contains all the different stages that can be executed in a process. It is a reference table that has unique identifiers for the different process stages and their description. These stages help to distinguish and classify the individual steps (events) that are taken in order to complete a process instance.

Table 3.6 outlines each field's attribute name, data type, description, and relational links.

Attribute	Type	Description	Relation
LawId	INT	The unique identifier of the process law.	FK → ProcessLaws
ProcessCategory	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the process category.	FK → ProcessCategories
ProcessSubCategory	INT	The unique identifier of the process sub category.	FK → ProcessSubCategories
ProcessStage	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the process stage.	PK
StageDescription	VARCHAR2	The description of the process stage.	-

Table 3.6: Attribute information of the Process Stages Table

3.2.7 Execution Reference

The Execution Reference table contains all the different execution states that a process instance can have. It is a reference table that has unique identifiers for the different executions states and their description.

Table 3.7 outlines each field's attribute name, data type, description, and relational links.

Attribute	Type	Description	Relation
ExecutionState	INT	The process instance execution status	PK
ExecutionDescription	VARCHAR2	The description of the execution status.	-

Table 3.7: Attribute information of the Execution Reference Table

3.2.8 Suspension Reference

The Suspension Reference table contains all the different suspension types that a process instance can have. It is a reference table that has unique identifiers for the different suspension types and their description. This table is key to track the reasons why a process instance might be suspended, which can have an impact on the deadline and overall timeline of the process.

Table 3.8 outlines each field's attribute name, data type, description, and relational links.

Attribute	Type	Description	Relation
SuspensionType	INT	The type of the suspension of the process instance.	PK
SuspensionDescription	VARCHAR2	The description of the suspension.	-

Table 3.8: Attribute information of the Suspension Reference Table

3.2.9 Result Reference

The Result Reference table contains all the different result types that a process instance or a process stage can have. It is a reference table that has unique identifiers for the different result types and their description.

Table 3.9 outlines each field's attribute name, data type, description, and relational links.

Attribute	Type	Description	Relation
ResultType	VARCHAR2	The type of the result.	PK
ResultDescription	VARCHAR2	The description of the result.	-

Table 3.9: Attribute information of the Result Reference Table

3.2.10 Stages Path

The Stages Path table specifies the possible transitions between the different process stages of a process. It is independent of the Process Status and Process History tables, which contain process instance and event data. In essence, this table describes the intended municipal workflow of a process, outlining for each current process stage what the possible next process stages within a process can be.

Table 3.10 outlines each field's attribute name, data type, description, and relational links.

Attribute	Type	Description	Relation
LawId	INT	The unique identifier of the process law.	FK → ProcessLaws
ProcessCategory	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the process category.	FK → ProcessCategories
ProcessSubCategory	INT	The unique identifier of the process sub category.	FK → ProcessSubCategories
ProcessStageFrom	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the current process stage.	FK → ProcessStages
ProcessStageTo	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the next process stage.	FK → ProcessStages

Table 3.10: Attribute information of the Stages Path Table

This section described the database schema, the attributes of the core tables, and explained the relationships between its core tables. The next section defines the process identifier used to partition the data into distinct processes.

3.3 Process Identifier

The raw process data in the database contains records from multiple, distinct processes within a municipality, and each process has its own workflow. To enable independent analysis, each process must be uniquely identified.

A process is distinguished by the combination of three attributes: *LawId*, *ProcessCategory*, and *ProcessSubCategory*. As shown in Figure 3.1, these attributes occur in every table storing information about process instances (cases), process stages (events), and workflows, ensuring each record can be linked to its corresponding process. Consequently, they are mandatory for both case and event attributes (Post. 5.2 and Post. 2.2).

To analyze processes in isolation, the formal event log definitions from Chapter 2 are extended with a *process identifier* and a *log partition* definition. This enables the complete event log to be divided into sub logs, each containing only the cases and events belonging to a single process. The process identifier is defined as:

Definition 14 (Process identifier).

Given an event log $L = (\mathcal{U}_e, \preceq)$ (Def. 3) and $C(L)$ be the set of cases in L (Def. 4).

A process-identifier function is a total map:

$$\pi : C(L) \longrightarrow P,$$

where P is a finite, non-empty set of process identifiers. Two cases $\sigma, \sigma' \in C(L)$ belong to the same process identifier iff $\pi(\sigma) = \pi(\sigma')$.

Further, let N be the number of characteristic process attributes and define:

$$\gamma : P \longrightarrow N,$$

as a total attribute function that assigns to each process identifier $p \in P$ a N -tuple of characteristic attributes.

Thus, for any case $\sigma \in C(L)$, the composition

$$\gamma(\pi(\sigma))$$

yields the characteristic attribute tuple for the process identifier to which σ belongs. ◁

Since the *LawId*, *ProcessCategory*, and *ProcessSubCategory* uniquely identify each process in the municipality data, they form the tuple of characteristic attributes in the process-identifier function. The following postulate formalizes the domain-specific process-identifier:

Postulate 14.1 (Domain-specific process identifier).

Let $\gamma : P \rightarrow N$ be the characteristic attribute function (Def. 14).

For all $p \in P$, $N = 3$ and the characteristic attribute tuple is

$$\gamma(p) = (\text{LawId}(p), \text{ProcessCategory}(p), \text{ProcessSubCategory}(p)),$$

where *LawId*, *ProcessCategory*, and *ProcessSubCategory* are total on P . ◁

Given the process-identifier, the event log can be partitioned into distinct sub logs, each containing only the cases and events associated with a single process. The log partition is defined as:

Definition 15 (Log partition).

Given an event log $L = (\mathcal{U}_e, \preceq)$ (Def. 3) and $C(L)$ be the set of cases in L (Def. 4). For any process identifier $p \in P$ induced by the process-identifier function π (Def. 14):

Let the set of cases of p be:

$$C_p := \{\sigma \in C(L) \mid \pi(\sigma) = p\}$$

where $C_p \subseteq C$ and let the set of events of p be:

$$E_p := \{e \in \mathcal{U}_e \mid \exists \sigma \in C_p : e \in \sigma\}$$

The log partition for a process identifier p is the pair:

$$L_p := (E_p, \preceq_p),$$

where \preceq_p is a total order restricting the log order \preceq over the events in E_p . ◁

This partitioning ensures that each sub log L_p contains only the information of a single process and can therefore be analyzed independently.

This section defined the process identifier used to partition the data into distinct processes. The next section discusses the dataset's limitations.

3.4 Data Limitations

The dataset has several limitations that should be noted:

1. The start dates that are recorded for the Process Status and Process History tables are only recorded as calendar dates, without any time indicator.
2. The underlying database included fields for legal end date and the potential extension of this end date. However, these columns were undefined and/or empty in the extractions that were provided in cooperation with different participating municipalities and have therefore been omitted from this study.
3. All descriptive values in the database are only stored in Dutch. A translation layer is required to ensure clarity for non-dutch speakers.
4. The Stages Path table contains no attributes indicating whether the possible next stages are intended to execute exclusively or in parallel. By default, municipal intended workflows are modeled using exclusive choices and do not include parallel execution.

This section discussed the dataset's limitations. The next section discusses the privacy and data-protection measures.

3.5 Privacy & Data Protection

Centric anonymized the data prior to extraction, ensuring no personal or sensitive information is present and maintaining compliance with privacy regulations.

In order to further preserve the intellectual property of Centric and prevent the disclosure of proprietary system details, the relevant tables and column names that are shown in Figure 3.1 have been mapped to generalized names.

These measures allow the dataset and analysis results to be published while preserving individual privacy and Centric's proprietary information.

This chapter provided a detailed description of the raw municipal process data that is used for this thesis. It outlined where the data came from, who provided it, what the data schema and relations are, how to identify different processes, and it discussed the limitations and privacy of the data.

The next chapter outlines the structural framework that is designed.

4 Municipal Process Analysis Framework

This chapter outlines the structural framework that is designed for analyzing municipal processes through process mining. The framework consists of a step-by-step approach to go from raw event data to eventual process diagnostics, which is the main research objective of this thesis. This objective was divided into three sub-objectives (see ??), each of which corresponds to a specific phase within the overall framework.

The framework is also divided into a public part and a private part. As mentioned in Chapter 3, the data is extracted in collaboration with municipalities that are connected with Centric and should be anonymized and generalized to comply with privacy regulations and prevent the disclosure of proprietary system details. Therefore, there are several steps of the framework that will not be disclosed and remain private.

The framework steps that are public are discussed in this chapter and these start with the raw process data that is already extracted, filtered to include only relevant tables and attributes, anonymized and generalized. This raw process data has the structure as defined in Section 3.2. This raw process data is split into the regulatory patterns data and the process event data. The regulatory patterns data is the Stages Path table from Section 3.2.10 and the process event data are all the other tables.

Figure 4.1 shows a high-level workflow of this framework, including an overview of the different steps of the framework, to which sub objective they belong and whether they are public (white) or private (gray) operations. This chapter describes the different public steps of the framework and is structured as follows:

Section 4.1 introduces the data preprocessing, Section 4.2 describes the transformation into regulatory patterns and event logs, Section 4.3 presents the generation of XES event logs, Section 4.4 details the normative process models generation, Section 4.5 outlines the descriptive process models discovery, Section 4.6 explains the conformance checking, and Section 4.7 concludes with the process diagnostics.

Figure 4.1: High-level Workflow of the Municipal Process Analysis Framework

4.1 Data Preprocessing

This section introduces the framework's data preprocessing step. To handle the challenges of real-world data, two datasets are created from the extracted process data: a processed dataset and a raw dataset. The processed dataset results from applying various preprocessing operations that improve data quality and cleans inaccurate or unnecessary data records. The raw dataset undergoes only the essential operations required to prepare the data for transformations, thereby remaining a faithful representation of the source data for comparison. The section is structured as follows:

Section 4.1.1 discusses the preprocessing of the regulatory patterns data and Section 4.1.2 discusses the preprocessing of the process event data.

4.1.1 Regulatory Patterns Data

The regulatory patterns are stored in the *StagesPath* table, which describes the intended municipal workflow for a process. This data outlines for each current process stage what the possible next process stages can be. As mentioned before in Section 3.1, a municipality is free to configure its own workflow for a process and there is no single standard execution path.

This means that each municipality creates its own set of process stages for the events of a given process and defines which subsequent process stages are possible for each stage. The connections are stored as separate rows in the Stage Path table, as the *ProcessStageFrom* and *ProcessStageTo* attributes. See Section 3.2.6 for an overview of the stages path attributes.

One problem that arises is that not every municipality defines a clear starting stage for a process, resulting in that there can be several different process stages within the workflow that are a starting point for the process, depending on the situation. It is not possible to determine from the regulatory patterns which process stage is the intended starting point of a process, without a predefined starting stage.

However, the potential starting process stages can be identified via the *ProcessStageTo* attribute of the stages path table. Since each row in this table represents a connection between two stages, any stage that never appears in this column has no preceding stages and is therefore considered a potential starting stage.

To solve the first problem of determining the actual starting stage, the preprocessing of these regulatory patterns includes defining an artificial starting stage in the cases where there is no explicit starting stage in the intended workflow of a process. This artificial starting stage is then connected to each of the potential starting stages via a new row in the stages path table. The artificial starting stage is added to the process stages table as well, which is the reference table for all the different stages that can be executed in a process.

Another problem that arises is that some municipalities, while defining a clear starting stage for a process, may still have other process stages which can not be reached via any path from the starting stage in the intended workflow. In essence, these process stages would themselves become alternate starting stages, and it is not possible to determine from the regulatory patterns how the process

can be initiated from these alternate starting stages.

To solve the second problem of alternate starting stages, the preprocessing of these regulatory patterns include connecting the intended starting stage of a process to each of the alternate starting stages via a new row in the stages path table. The intended and alternate starting stages are already defined, thus they do not need to be added to the process stages table.

As mentioned before in Section 3.3, the data contains information about several distinct processes. Therefore, the preprocessing of the regulatory patterns needs to be executed for each individual process. Each process can be identified by the process identifier, which is the combination of the *LawId*, *ProcessCategory*, and *ProcessSubCategory* attributes (Post. 14.1).

Algorithm 1 shows in pseudo code how the preprocessing of the regulatory patterns is handled. The intended and artificial starting stages of a process have a *ProcessStage* value of 0.

Algorithm 1: Preprocessing of the Regulatory Patterns

Input: *StagesPaths* table; *ProcessStages* table.

Output: Updated *StagesPaths* (with artificial starting stage paths); Updated *ProcessStages* (with artificial starting stage).

Pre-condition : The *StagesPaths* and *ProcessStages* are well-formed w.r.t. the format described in Table 3.10 and Table 3.6, respectively.

```

1 Function PreprocessRegulatoryPatterns (StagesPaths,ProcessStages)
2   foreach process in unique processes of StagesPaths do
3     | StagesPathsp ← filter StagesPaths for process
4     | ProcessStagesp ← filter ProcessStages for process
5     | StagesPaths ← merge CreateStartPaths (StagesPathsp)
6     | ProcessStages ← merge CreateStartStage (ProcessStagesp)
7   end
8   return StagesPaths,ProcessStages

9 Function CreateStartPaths (StagesPathsp)
10  | potentialStartStages ← {ProcessStageFrom} \ {ProcessStageTo}
11  | foreach stage in potentialStartStages do
12  |   | if stage ≠ 0 then
13  |   |   | StagesPathsp ← add entry {ProcessStageFrom = 0, ProcessStageTo = stage}
14  |   end
15  | return StagesPathsp

16 Function CreateStartStage (ProcessStagesp)
17  | if ProcessStage = 0 not in ProcessStagesp then
18  |   | ProcessStagesp ← add entry
18  |   |   | {ProcessStage = 0, StageDescription = "Start Work Process"}
19  | return ProcessStagesp

```

Note that this operation is only done for the processed dataset, the raw dataset does not get the artificial starting stages and stays the same as the original data.

This subsection detailed the preprocessing operations for the pattern data, the next subsection will discuss the preprocessing operations for the event data.

4.1.2 Process Event Data

There are several different operations that need to be done for the preprocessing of the process event data. As mentioned in Section 3.2, the process status and process history tables contain the data related to the different process instances (cases) and events of the municipal processes respectively.

The preprocessing of the event data focuses on these two tables. See Section 3.2.1 for an overview of the attributes of the process status table and see Section 3.2.2 for an overview the attributes of the process history table.

The different preprocessing operations are detailed below. The operations ranging from 4.1.2.1 to 4.1.2.7 are aimed at improving the quality of the data and removing the unnecessary and inaccurate data records, which result in the processed dataset. The remaining operations 4.1.2.8 and 4.1.2.9 are essential for both the processed and the raw dataset.

4.1.2.1 Filter finished process instances

The first operation removes all the process instances which are not finished from the dataset. Since these process instances are not completed, their traces are incomplete as well, which will interfere with the discovering a process model of the process [3].

Every process instance has a mandatory attribute *ExecutionState* (Post. 5.2), which contains the information of the current state for that process instance. This attribute is used to filter out all the process instances that are not finished, based on the value of the execution state. Once all the process instances are filtered out, the corresponding events records of the removed process instances that are stored in the process history table are filtered out as well.

Algorithm 2 shows in pseudo code how the preprocessing of the finished process instances is handled. The finished process instances have a *ExecutionState* value of 8.

Algorithm 2: Preprocessing of the Finished Process Instances

Input: *ProcessStatus* table; *ProcessHistory* table.

Output: Filtered *ProcessStatus* (containing only finished process instances); Filtered *ProcessHistory* (containing only events corresponding to the filtered process instances).

Pre-condition : The *ProcessStatus* and *ProcessHistory* are well-formed w.r.t. the format described in Table 3.1 and Table 3.2, respectively.

```

1 Function FilterFinishedProcessInstances(ProcessStatus,ProcessHistory)
2   ProcessStatus ← filter ProcessStatus where ExecutionState = 8
3   validCaseIds ← extract CaseId from ProcessStatus
4   ProcessHistory ← filter ProcessHistory where CaseId ∈ validCaseIds
5   return ProcessStatus,ProcessHistory

```

4.1.2.2 Filter early process instances

The second operation removes all the process instances that started before a certain time threshold. The dataset that is provided by the different municipalities is extracted from the database for a certain time period. The dataset includes the process instances in the process status table which started before this time period, but finished during this time period.

The problem that arises is that, since the process instance was started before the time period, the events of those process instances that occurred before the time period, are not included in the Process History table. In other words, the traces of these process instances can be incomplete, as there could be preceding events that are not included in the dataset.

Every process instance has a *StartDate* attribute, which contains the starting date of the process instance. This attribute is used to filter out all the process instances that started before a certain threshold. This threshold depends on the actual time period of the slice of the dataset. Once all the process instances are filtered out, the corresponding events records of the removed processes that are in stored in the process history table are filtered out as well.

Algorithm 3 shows in pseudo code how the preprocessing of the early process instances is handled.

Algorithm 3: Preprocessing of the Early Process Instances

Input: *ProcessStatus* table; *ProcessHistory* table.

Parameter: *threshold* (date for filtering early process instances).

Output: Filtered *ProcessStatus* (containing only process instances with $StartDate \geq$ threshold); Filtered *ProcessHistory* (containing only events corresponding to the filtered process instances).

Pre-condition : The *ProcessStatus* and *ProcessHistory* are well-formed w.r.t. the format described in Table 3.1 and Table 3.2, respectively.

```
1 Function FilterEarlyProcessInstances(ProcessStatus,ProcessHistory,threshold)
2   ProcessStatus  $\leftarrow$  filter ProcessStatus where  $StartDate \geq$  threshold
3   validCaseIds  $\leftarrow$  extract CaseId from ProcessStatus
4   ProcessHistory  $\leftarrow$  filter ProcessHistory where  $CaseId \in$  validCaseIds
5   return ProcessStatus,ProcessHistory
```

4.1.2.3 Filter invalid end dates

The third operation removes all the process instances that have invalid end dates. Each process instance has a *StartDate* attribute and a *End Date* attribute, indicating the start and end date of the process instance.

However, in some cases, the *StartDate* of a process instance is later than its *EndDate*, due to unknown causes in the reporting system. This indicates a data quality issue in the dataset, therefore these process instances will be excluded from the dataset to prevent prevent inconsistencies in later stages of the framework. Once all these process instances are filtered out, the corresponding events records of the removed processes that are in stored in the process history table are filtered out as well.

Algorithm 4 shows in pseudo code how the preprocessing of the invalid end dates is handled.

Algorithm 4: Preprocessing of the Invalid End Dates

Input: *ProcessStatus* table; *ProcessHistory* table.

Output: Filtered *ProcessStatus* (containing only process instances where $EndDate \geq StartDate$) and *ProcessHistory* (containing only events corresponding to those process instances).

Pre-condition : The *ProcessStatus* and *ProcessHistory* are well-formed w.r.t. the format described in Table 3.1 and Table 3.2, respectively.

```

1 Function FilterInvalidEndDates(ProcessStatus,ProcessHistory)
2   ProcessStatus  $\leftarrow$  filter ProcessStatus where  $EndDate \geq StartDate$ 
3   validCaseIds  $\leftarrow$  extract CaseId from ProcessStatus
4   ProcessHistory  $\leftarrow$  filter ProcessHistory where  $CaseId \in \text{validCaseIds}$ 
5   return ProcessStatus,ProcessHistory

```

4.1.2.4 Filter undefined process stages

The fourth operation removes all the events that have undefined process stages. Each event record has an attribute *ProcessStage*, which is the unique identifier of the process stage that is executed during the event.

However, in some cases, the dataset contains events where the *ProcessStage* is empty or undefined due to unknown causes in the reporting system. Since *ProcessStage* is a mandatory event attribute (Post. 2.1), such events are considered a data quality issue and are excluded to avoid ambiguities regarding the executed process stage and to ensure consistency in the later stages of the framework.

Even though the current dataset is not yet an actual event log, the removal of these events is similar to the projection pre-processing operation on an event log, which removes events that do not satisfy a specific property [35].

Algorithm 5 shows in pseudo code how the preprocessing of the undefined process stages is handled.

Algorithm 5: Preprocessing of the Undefined Events

Input: *ProcessHistory* table.

Output: Filtered *ProcessHistory* (containing only events with a valid *ProcessStage*).

Pre-condition : The *ProcessHistory* is well-formed w.r.t. the format described in Table 3.2.

```

1 Function FilterInvalidEvents(ProcessHistory)
2   ProcessHistory  $\leftarrow$  filter ProcessHistory where  $ProcessStage \neq \text{N/A}$ 
3   ProcessHistory  $\leftarrow$  filter ProcessHistory where  $ProcessStage \neq ""$ 
4   return ProcessHistory

```

4.1.2.5 Filter missing closing stages

The fifth operation removes all the process instances that have no event records with a closing stage. The process instances that are currently left in the dataset are all finished, since the unfinished process instances are filtered out in the first operation of the preprocessing (see Section 4.1.2.1).

However, in some cases, process instances are present that lack a closing stage. This indicates a data quality issue in the dataset, as a different process stage becomes the final recorded event for the instance. The workflow of a process within a municipality has a clear intended closing stage, and no other process stage can validly be the last for a finished process instance. Therefore, these process instances are filtered out to ensure consistency in the later stages of the framework.

Even though the current dataset is not yet an actual event log, the removal of these process instances is similar to the selection pre-processing operation on an event log, which removes traces that do not satisfy a specific property [35].

Once all the process instances are filtered out, the corresponding events records of the removed process instances that are stored in the process history table are filtered out as well.

Algorithm 6 shows in pseudo code how the preprocessing of the missing closing stages is handled. The intended closing stages of the processes have a *ProcessStage* value of 99.

Algorithm 6: Preprocessing of the Missing Closing Stages

Input: *ProcessStatus* table; *ProcessHistory* table.

Output: Filtered *ProcessStatus* (containing only process instances with a valid closing stage);
 Filtered *ProcessHistory* (containing only events corresponding to the filtered process instances).

Pre-condition : The *ProcessStatus* and *ProcessHistory* are well-formed w.r.t. the format described in Table 3.1 and Table 3.2, respectively.

```

1 Function FilterClosedProcessInstances(ProcessStatus,ProcessHistory)
2   closedCaseIds  $\leftarrow$  extract CaseId from ProcessHistory where ProcessStage = 99
3   ProcessStatus  $\leftarrow$  filter ProcessStatus where CaseId  $\in$  closedCaseIds
4   ProcessHistory  $\leftarrow$  filter ProcessHistory where CaseId  $\in$  closedCaseIds
5   return ProcessStatus,ProcessHistory

```

4.1.2.6 Filter misclassified events

The sixth operation removes all events from the process history table that are misclassified. An event is considered misclassified if it is linked to a case whose process identifier does not match the process-related attributes of the event itself.

As defined in Section 3.3, a process is uniquely identified by the combination of the *LawId*, *ProcessCategory*, and *ProcessSubCategory* attributes. Since each event belongs to a specific case, it must share the same process identifier as that case.

However, in some cases, events exist in the process history table whose *CaseId* matches an existing process instance in the process status table, yet whose process identifier attributes indicate they belong to a different process. The exact cause is unknown, but the most likely explanation is that a previous process instance was canceled and a new process instance was started for the same client using the same *CaseId*, which should not be allowed but might be possible in the reporting system.

Due to these events being misclassified and not actually belonging to the current process instance with that *CaseId*, they are filtered out from the dataset.

Algorithm 7 shows the preprocessing of misclassified events. It uses the *CaseId* together with the process identifier attributes to remove events that have no corresponding process instance in the process status table.

Algorithm 7: Preprocessing of the Misclassified Events

Input: *ProcessStatus* table; *ProcessHistory* table.

Output: Filtered *ProcessHistory* (containing only events where *CaseId*, *LawId*, *ProcessCategory*, and *ProcessSubCategory* match a corresponding process instance in *ProcessStatus*).

Pre-condition : The *ProcessStatus* and *ProcessHistory* are well-formed w.r.t. the format described in Table 3.1 and Table 3.2, respectively.

```

1 Function FilterMisclassified(ProcessStatus,ProcessHistory)
2   validCases ← extract (CaseId,LawId,ProcessCategory,ProcessSubCategory) from
   ProcessStatus
3   ProcessHistory ← filter ProcessHistory where
   (CaseId,LawId,ProcessCategory,ProcessSubCategory) ∈ validCases
4   return ProcessHistory

```

4.1.2.7 Create new start events

The seventh operation is creating start event records. As described in Section 4.1.1, the preprocessing of the regulatory patterns extends the intended workflows of the processes with artificial starting stages.

The actual events corresponding to these artificial starting stages do not yet exist in the process history table. For each process instance in the process status table that lacks a starting stage event, a new event record is added to the process history table.

Each new event record requires the initialization of several attributes. Since this event represents the starting stage, it must be the first event of the process instance. Therefore, its *StartDate* is set to the *StartDate* recorded for the process instance, and its *EndDate* is set to the same value, as the starting stage is executed instantaneously.

Below is a list of all the attributes and what values they are assigned:

<i>HistoryId</i>	→	Newly generated unique identifier.
<i>CaseId</i>	→	Copied from the corresponding process instance.
<i>StartDate</i>	→	Copied from the corresponding process instance.
<i>EndDate</i>	→	Set equal to the <i>StartDate</i> .
<i>LawId</i>	→	Copied from the corresponding process instance.
<i>ProcessCategory</i>	→	Copied from the corresponding process instance.
<i>ProcessSubCategory</i>	→	Copied from the corresponding process instance.
<i>ProcessStage</i>	→	Fixed value for starting stage (0).
<i>TeamId</i>	→	Copied from the corresponding process instance.
<i>EmployeeId</i>	→	Copied from the corresponding process instance.
<i>ResultType</i>	→	Standard completion result ("ZZ").

Algorithm 8 shows in pseudo code how the preprocessing of the misclassified events is handled.

Algorithm 8: Creation of New Start Events

Input: *ProcessStatus* table; *ProcessHistory* table.

Output: Updated *ProcessHistory* (with start events for each process instance).

Pre-condition : The *ProcessStatus* and *ProcessHistory* are well-formed w.r.t. the format described in Table 3.1 and Table 3.2, respectively.

```

1 Function CreateStartEvents(ProcessStatus,ProcessHistory)
2   startedCaseIds ← extract CaseId from ProcessHistory where ProcessStage = 0
3   allCaseIds ← extract CaseId from ProcessStatus
4   foreach CaseId in allCaseIds do
5     | if CaseId not in startedCaseIds then
6     | | ProcessHistory ← add new starting event record
7   end
8   return ProcessHistory

```

4.1.2.8 Create lifecycle transitions

The seventh operation is the addition of lifecycle transitions to the events in the process history table. This operation is executed for both the processed and the raw dataset.

Each event corresponds the execution of a specific process stage and when an event is completed they get a *ResultType* and the workflow of the process instance continues. However, it is not necessarily the case that each event execution within a process instance gets a *ResultType* and is completed. It is possible that there are multiple occurrences of an event in a process instance that are part of the same execution of a process stage, i.e., part of the same activity instance.

The addition of lifecycle transitions to the events is a way to annotate each event with a label that reflects the state of the execution of the process stage. An execution of a process stage is only considered finished when the event record has a *ResultType*, otherwise it is considered to be ongoing.

This preprocessing operation enriches each event in a process instance with a lifecycle label that reflects the current state of its process stage. Table 4.1 lists each transition, its associated state, and a brief description.

Transition	State	Description
Start	Active	The execution of the process stage is started.
Continue	Active / Suspended	The execution of the process stage continues.
Reassign	Active	The execution of the process stage is reassigned to another resource.
Suspend	Suspended	The execution of the process stage is suspended.
Resume	Active	The execution of the process stage is resumed.
Complete	Finished	The execution of the process stage is completed successfully.
Terminate	Finished	The execution of the process stage is terminated unsuccessfully.

Table 4.1: Overview of lifecycle transitions.

The lifecycle transitions only depend on the other events inside of a process instance. Since the events of a process instance are ordered by their timestamp (Def. 4), the assigning of the lifecycle transition proceeds strictly from the first event to the last event in the process instance.

Algorithm 9 shows the pseudo code logic that is applied to each event to determine the lifecycle transition. The list below explains the steps of that logic in detail, including for each step an example trace with the lifecycle transition written as subscript to the activity label:

1. If the current event has a non-empty *ResultType*, the process stage state is marked as *finished* and the current event gets the lifecycle transition of *Complete*.

Example: $\langle a_{\text{complete}}, b_{\text{complete}}, c_{\text{complete}}, d_{\text{complete}} \rangle$

2. If the process stage has an *uninitialized* state or a *finished* state, the process stage state is marked *active* and the current event gets the lifecycle transition of *Start*. There can be several distinct activity instances of the same process stage that are not part of the same lifecycle, so a second activity instance of that process stage may be started even if a previous instance has already been finished.

Example: $\langle a_{\text{start}}, a_{\text{complete}}, b_{\text{complete}}, a_{\text{start}}, a_{\text{complete}}, b_{\text{complete}}, c_{\text{complete}} \rangle$

3. If the process stage has an *active* state:

- (a) If the next event has the same process stage:

- i. If the current event has different resources that handled the execution than the previous event, it gets the lifecycle transition of *Reassign*.

Example: $\langle a_{\text{start}}, a_{\text{reassign}}, a_{\text{complete}}, b_{\text{complete}}, c_{\text{complete}} \rangle$

- ii. If there is no change compared to the previous event, it gets the lifecycle transition of *Continue*.

Example: $\langle a_{\text{start}}, a_{\text{continue}}, a_{\text{complete}}, b_{\text{complete}}, c_{\text{complete}} \rangle$

- (b) If there is an event with the same process stage later in the process instance, the process stage state is marked *suspended* and the current event gets the lifecycle transition of *Suspended*.

Example: $\langle a_{\text{start}}, a_{\text{suspend}}, b_{\text{complete}}, c_{\text{complete}}, a_{\text{complete}} \rangle$

- (c) If there is no other event with the same process stage in the process instance, the process stage state is marked *finished* and the current event gets the lifecycle transition of *Terminate*.

Example: $\langle a_{\text{start}}, a_{\text{terminate}}, b_{\text{complete}}, c_{\text{complete}}, d_{\text{complete}} \rangle$

4. If the process stage has an *suspended* state:

- (a) If the next event has the same process stage, the process stage state is marked *active* and the current event gets the lifecycle transition of *Resume*.

Example: $\langle a_{\text{start}}, a_{\text{suspend}}, b_{\text{complete}}, a_{\text{resume}}, a_{\text{complete}}, c_{\text{complete}} \rangle$

- (b) If there is an event with the same process stage later in the process instance, the process stage state remains *suspended* and the current event gets the lifecycle transition *Continue*.

Example: $\langle a_{\text{start}}, a_{\text{suspend}}, b_{\text{complete}}, a_{\text{continue}}, c_{\text{complete}}, a_{\text{complete}} \rangle$

- (c) If there is no other event with the same process stage in the process instance, the state is marked *finished* and the current event gets the lifecycle transition of *Terminate*.

Example: $\langle a_{\text{start}}, a_{\text{suspend}}, b_{\text{complete}}, a_{\text{terminate}}, c_{\text{complete}}, d_{\text{complete}} \rangle$

Algorithm 9: Lifecycle Transition Assignment Logic (1/2)

```
IF result:
  State := FINISHED
  LifTr := COMPLETE

ELSE IF State is FINISHED or State is  $\perp$ :
  State := ACTIVE
  LifTr := START

ELSE IF State is ACTIVE:
  IF same_event_next:
    IF different_resources_prev:
      State := ACTIVE
      LifTr := REASSIGN
    ELSE:
      State := ACTIVE
      LifTr := CONTINUE

  ELSE IF same_event_later:
    State := SUSPENDED
    LifTr := SUSPEND
  ELSE:
    State := FINISHED
    LifTr := TERMINATE

ELSE IF State is SUSPENDED:
  IF same_event_next:
    State := ACTIVE
    LifTr := RESUME

  ELSE IF same_event_later:
    State := SUSPENDED
    LifTr := CONTINUE
  ELSE:
    State := FINISHED
    LifTr := TERMINATE
```

4.1.2.9 Create identifiers

The final operation adds numerical unique identifiers to the process instances in the process status table and the events in the process history table. This operation is applied to both the processed and raw datasets.

Although process instances have a unique *CaseId* and events have a unique *HistoryId*, these identifiers are often long or non-numeric. New identifiers are therefore generated for each process instance and event in a simple numerical form, enforcing a clear and monotonic ordering for the later stages of the framework.

The identifiers are numbered sequentially, with process instances receiving a "T" prefix and events receiving an "E" prefix. Algorithm 10 shows in pseudo code how these identifiers are added.

This section explained the preprocessing of both the regulatory patterns data and the process event data, detailing the operations involved. The result is two parallel datasets: a raw dataset, which undergoes only the essential operations, and a processed dataset, which incorporates the full set of preprocessing operations. The next chapter introduces the data transformation step of the framework.

Algorithm 10: Creation of New Identifiers

Input: *ProcessStatus* table; *ProcessHistory* table.

Output: Updated *ProcessStatus* (with a new numerical *InstanceId* for each process instance); Updated *ProcessHistory* (with a new numerical *EventId* for each event).

Pre-condition : The *ProcessStatus* and *ProcessHistory* are well-formed w.r.t. the format described in Table 3.1 and Table 3.2, respectively.

```
1 Function CreateIdentifiers(ProcessStatus,ProcessHistory)
2   for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $|ProcessStatus|$  do
3      $ProcessStatus[i].InstanceId \leftarrow "T\{i\}"$ 
4   end
5   for  $j \leftarrow 1$  to  $|ProcessHistory|$  do
6      $ProcessHistory[j].EventId \leftarrow "E\{j\}"$ 
7   end
8   return ProcessStatus,ProcessHistory
```

4.2 Data Transformation

In the previous step, the framework produced the raw and processed datasets, consisting of multiple tables that must now be transformed into formal event logs and regulatory patterns. This transformation involves combining the relevant tables, adding translations, and partitioning them into logs that contain information about a single process only. The section is structured as follows:

Section 4.2.1 discusses the transformation of the regulatory patterns data and Section 4.2.2 discusses the transformation of the process event data.

The following transformation operations are used on both the raw and the processed datasets.

4.2.1 Regulatory Patterns Data

The regulatory patterns data defines the intended municipal workflow for a process. However, the stages path table contains the attributes *ProcessStageFrom* and *ProcessStageTo*, which are only the unique identifiers for process stages and do not include their descriptions.

The first operation is to enrich the stages path table by merging it with the process stages table, which serves as a reference containing the descriptions of each process stage. This produces a regulatory patterns table with the actual stage descriptions, which are then translated and added as additional columns.

The second operation is to partition the regulatory patterns table into sub tables, each containing the data for a single process identifier. As defined earlier (Post. 14.1), the process identifier is the combination of *LawId*, *ProcessCategory*, and *ProcessSubCategory*.

Table 4.2 outlines the schema of the Regulatory Patterns table, including all attribute names, types, and descriptions.

Attribute	Type	Description
LawId	INT	The unique identifier of the process law.
ProcessCategory	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the process category.
ProcessSubCategory	INT	The unique identifier of the process sub category.
ProcessStageFrom	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the current process stage.
ProcessStageTo	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the next process stage.
StageDescriptionFromNL	VARCHAR2	The dutch description of the current process stage.
StageDescriptionToNL	VARCHAR2	The dutch description of the next process stage.
StageDescriptionFromEN	VARCHAR2	The english description of the current process stage.
StageDescriptionToEN	VARCHAR2	The english description of the next process stage.

Table 4.2: Attribute information of the Regulatory Patterns.

Notice that the process identifier attribute descriptions are not added to this table, as they hold no additional value for the regulatory patterns.

This subsection covered the transformation of the pattern data, the next subsection will cover the transformation of the event data.

4.2.2 Process Event Data

The process event data consists of multiple tables, including the process status table, which contains data about individual process instances (cases), and the process history table, which contains the events of these process instances. In addition, several reference tables store descriptive information related to various attributes. The transformation operations below describe how the process event data is converted into event logs.

The first operation is to enrich the process status and process history tables with descriptive attributes from their corresponding reference tables.

As shown in Table 3.1, several attributes in the process status table reference a separate table containing descriptive information. In this step, these descriptions are added to the process status table. The descriptive attributes include: *LawDescription*, *CategoryDescription*, *SubCategoryDescription*, *ExecutionDescription*, *SuspensionDescription*, and *ResultDescription*.

Similarly, as shown in Table 3.2, several attributes in the process history table also reference descriptive information from other tables. These descriptions, which include *StageDescription* and *ResultDescription*, are added to the process history table. The process identifier attributes are not enriched here, as their descriptions are already included in the process status table, and these tables will be combined in the next operation.

Because all original descriptions are in Dutch, both the process status and process history tables are extended with additional attributes containing the English translations of these descriptions.

The second operation is to combine the enriched process status and process history tables into a single event log. The following steps detail how this is done:

1. Each event in the process history table, along with its attributes, becomes one row in the event log.
2. For each row, the corresponding attributes from the related process instance are added based on the *CaseId*.
3. The process identifier attributes *LawId*, *ProcessCategory*, and *ProcessSubCategory* are merged, as both the event and the process instance contain equivalent values for these attributes.
4. Several other attributes share the same name in both the process instance and the event but must remain distinct. In such cases, the event attributes are given the prefix "*Stage*" and the process instance attributes the prefix "*Case*".

The resulting event log contains all the information of the process instances and the events combined.

The third operation is to partition the event log into sub event logs, each containing only the data for a single process. As defined earlier (Post. 14.1), the process identifier is the combination of *LawId*, *ProcessCategory*, and *ProcessSubCategory*.

Table 4.3 outlines the layout of an event log, including all the attribute names, types and descriptions.

This section covered the transformation of the pattern data into the regulatory patterns and the transformation of the event data into event logs. These transformation operations are carried out on both the raw and the processed datasets. The next section will introduce the XES event log generation step of the framework.

Attribute	Type	Description
CaseId	INT	The unique identifier of each process instance.
LawId	INT	The unique identifier of the process law.
LawDescriptionNL	VARCHAR2	The description of the process law in dutch.
LawDescriptionEN	VARCHAR2	The description of the process law in english.
ProcessCategory	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the process category.
CategoryDescriptionNL	VARCHAR2	The description of the process category in dutch.
CategoryDescriptionEN	VARCHAR2	The description of the process category in english.
ProcessSubCategory	INT	The unique identifier of the process sub category.
SubCategoryDescriptionNL	VARCHAR2	The description of the process sub category in dutch.
SubCategoryDescriptionEN	VARCHAR2	The description of the process sub category in english.
InstanceId	VARCHAR2	The unique sequential identifier of the process instance.
CaseStartDate	DATETIME	The starting date of the process instance.
CaseEndDate	DATETIME	The ending date of the process instance.
CaseTeamId	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the responsible team of the process instance.
CaseEmployeeId	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the responsible employee of the process instance.
CaseExecutionState	INT	The execution status of the process instance.
CaseExecutionDescriptionNL	VARCHAR2	The description of the execution status in dutch.
CaseExecutionDescriptionEN	VARCHAR2	The description of the execution status in english.
CaseResultType	VARCHAR2	The type of the result of the process instance.
CaseResultDescriptionNL	VARCHAR2	The description of the process instance result in dutch.
CaseResultDescriptionEN	VARCHAR2	The description of the process instance result in english.
CaseSuspensionType	INT	The type of the suspension of the process instance.
CaseSuspensionDescriptionNL	VARCHAR2	The description of the suspension in dutch.
CaseSuspensionDescriptionEN	VARCHAR2	The description of the suspension in english.
EventId	VARCHAR2	The unique sequential identifier of the stage.
ProcessStage	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the process stage.
StageDescriptionNL	VARCHAR2	The description of the process stage in dutch.
StageDescriptionEN	VARCHAR2	The description of the process stage in english.
StageStartDate	DATETIME	The starting date of the stage.
StageEndDate	DATETIME	The ending date of the stage.
StageTeamId	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the responsible team of the stage.
StageEmployeeId	VARCHAR2	The unique identifier of the responsible employee of the stage.
StageResultType	VARCHAR2	The type of the result of the stage.
StageResultDescriptionNL	VARCHAR2	The description of the stage result in dutch.
StageResultDescriptionEN	VARCHAR2	The description of the stage result in english.
Lifecycle	VARCHAR2	The lifecycle transition of the stage.

Table 4.3: Attribute information of the Event Log

4.3 XES event logs

As explained in Section 2.1.4, the XES standard is XML-based and regulates the syntax and the semantics of the data.

The XES event logs are generated using the sub events logs, which are created in the previous transformation step. The generation of the XES event log is divided into several operation, which are detailed below:

The first operation of the XES generation is declaring the extensions that are being used. These extensions are primarily used to attach semantics to the attributes. The following five extensions are used:

1. **Concept:** introduces the attribute `concept:name` for logs, traces, and events, which is the generally understood name.
2. **Time:** introduces the attribute `time:timestamp` to record the time occurrence of each event.
3. **Lifecycle:** introduces the attribute `lifecycle:transition` that captures the transition and state of each event.
4. **Organizational:** introduces the attribute `org:resource`, and `org:group` to identify the resource and the group that executed the event.
5. **Identity:** introduces the attribute `identity:id` as an unique identifiers for logs, traces and events.

The second operation of the XES generation is declaring the global attributes, which are the attributes that remain constant across all traces and events. These attributes capture the context of the entire process. The following attributes of the event log are used as global attributes:

- **concept:name:** the concatenated process identifier attributes (*LawId_CategoryId_SubcategoryId*), serving as the process name.
- **Law attributes:** *LawId, LawDescriptionNL, LawDescriptionEN*
- **Category attributes:** *CategoryId, CategoryDescriptionNL, CategoryDescriptionEN*
- **Subcategory attributes:** *SubcategoryId, SubcategoryDescriptionNL, SubcategoryDescriptionEN*

The third operation of the XES generation is declaring the trace attributes, which are the attributes that remain constant across all events. These attributes capture the context of the entire trace. The following attributes of the event log are used as trace attributes:

- **concept:name:** the *CaseId* attribute, serving as the name of the trace.
- **org:resource:** the *CaseEmployeeId* attribute, serving as the resource of the trace.
- **org:group:** the *CaseTeamId* attribute, serving as the group of the trace.
- **identity:id:** the *InstanceId* attribute, serving as the unique identifier of the trace.
- **Time attributes:** *CaseStartDate, CaseEndDate.*
- **Execution attributes:** *ExecutionState, ExecutionDescriptionNL, ExecutionDescriptionEN*
- **Result attributes:** *CaseResultType, ResultDescriptionNL, CaseResultDescriptionEN*
- **Suspension attributes:** *CaseSuspensionType, SuspensionDescriptionNL, CaseSuspensionDescriptionEN*

The fourth operation of the XES generation is declaring the event attributes. These attributes capture the context of the event. The following attributes of the event log are used as event attributes:

- **concept:name:** the *StageDescriptionEn* attribute, serving as the name of the executed activity of the event.
- **time:timestamp:** the *StageEndDate* attribute, serving as the recorded time occurrence.
- **org:resource:** the *StageEmployeeId* attribute, serving as the resource who executed the event.
- **org:group:** the *StageTeamId* attribute, serving as the team who executed the event.
- **identity:id:** the *EventId* attribute, serving as the unique identifier of the event.
- **lifecycle:transition:** the *Lifecycle* attribute, capturing the transition and state of the event.
- **Time attributes:** *StageStartDate*
- **Result attributes:** *StageResultType*, *CaseResultDescriptionNL*, *CaseResultDescriptionEN*
- **Stage attributes:** *ProcessStage*, *StageDescriptionNL*

Additionally, a new attribute *WorkItemId* is added the event attributes. This identifier groups all events belonging to the same lifecycle together. It remains constant while the execution of a process stage is ongoing and increments only when that it reaches a complete or terminate transition. In this way, all events that share the same *WorkItemId* correspond to one contiguous execution of a process stage, i.e., an activity instance.

The final operation of the XES generation is declaring the classifiers that are being used. A classifier partitions events according to specific attributes, enabling multiple perspectives on the process. The following classifiers are defined:

1. **Activity:** uses the *concept:name* and *lifecycle:transition* attributes to group events by the english stage descriptions.
2. **Activity_Code:** uses the *ProcessStage* and *lifecycle:transition* attributes to group events by process stage identifier.
3. **Activity_Description_NL:** uses the *StageDescriptionNL* and *lifecycle:transition* attributes to group events by the dutch stage descriptions.
4. **Work_Item:** uses *workItemId* to group events belonging to the same lifecycle.
5. **Resource:** uses *org:resource* to group events by the executing employee.
6. **Group:** uses *org:group* to group events by the responsible team.

Now that all extensions, attributes, and classifiers are declared, the XES event logs can be created. Each sub event log containing the information of one process, that is created in the previous transformation step of the framework, is used to create an XES event log.

The XES event logs are created for both the raw and the processed event logs. Algorithm 11 shows in pseudo code how the XES event logs are created.

This section provided an overview of the generation of the XES event logs from the raw and processed events logs. The next section will cover the normative models generation step of the framework.

Algorithm 11: Generation of a XES Event Log (Part 1/2).

Input: $event_log$.

Output: \mathcal{L} : a fully structured XES event log with extensions, global attributes, trace attributes, event attributes, and classifiers.

Pre-condition : The $event_log$ is well-formed w.r.t. the format described in Table 2.1.

Global variable: $work_item_counter \leftarrow 1$ (initial counter for assigning work item IDs).

```
1 Function BuildXES( $event\_log$ )
2    $\mathcal{L} \leftarrow \text{NewXESLog}()$  // Step 1
3   DeclareExtensions( $\mathcal{L}$ , [Concept, Time, Lifecycle, Organizational, Identity])
4   SetGlobalAttributes( $\mathcal{L}$ ,  $event\_log$ , [concept:name, LawId, LawDescriptionNL,
   LawDescriptionEN, CategoryId, CategoryDescriptionNL,
   CategoryDescriptionEN, SubcategoryId, SubcategoryDescriptionNL,
   SubcategoryDescriptionEN]) // Step 2
5   foreach  $Case$  in  $event\_log$  do
6      $\tau \leftarrow \text{NewTrace}()$  // Step 3
7     SetTraceAttributes( $\tau$ , [concept:name, org:resource, org:group,
   identity:id, CaseStartDate, CaseEndDate, ExecutionState,
   ExecutionDescriptionNL, ExecutionDescriptionEN, CaseResultType,
   ResultDescriptionNL, CaseResultDescriptionEN, CaseSuspensionType,
   SuspensionDescriptionNL, CaseSuspensionDescriptionEN])
8      $Case \leftarrow \text{AssignWorkItemIds}(Case)$ 
9     foreach  $Event$  in  $Case$  do
10       $e \leftarrow \text{NewEvent}()$  // Step 4
11      SetEventAttributes( $e$ , [concept:name, time:timestamp, org:resource,
   org:group, identity:id, lifecycle:transition, StageStartDate,
   StageResultType, CaseResultDescriptionNL,
   CaseResultDescriptionEN, ProcessStage, StageDescriptionNL,
   WorkItemId])
12      append  $e \rightarrow \tau$ 
13    end
14    append  $\tau \rightarrow \mathcal{L}$ 
15  end // Step 5
16  DeclareClassifiers( $\mathcal{L}$ , Activity=(concept:name,lifecycle:transition),
   Activity_Code=(ProcessStage,lifecycle:transition),
   Activity_Description_NL=(StageDescriptionNL,lifecycle:transition),
   Work_Item=(WorkItemId, Resource=(org:resource), Group=(org:group)))
17  return  $\mathcal{L}$ 
```

Algorithm 11: Generation of a XES Event Log (Part 2/2).

```
17 .....
18 Function AssignWorkItemIds(Case)
19   suspended  $\leftarrow \emptyset$ 
20   foreach event in Case do
21     if event.Lifecycle  $\in \{Start, Reassign, Continue\}$  then
22       | event.WorkItemId  $\leftarrow$  work_item_counter
23     else if event.Lifecycle = Suspend then
24       | event.WorkItemId  $\leftarrow$  work_item_counter
25       | suspended[event.ProcessStage]  $\leftarrow$  work_item_counter
26     else if event.Lifecycle = Resume then
27       | event.WorkItemId  $\leftarrow$  suspended[event.ProcessStage]
28     if event.Lifecycle  $\in \{Complete, Terminate\}$  then
29       | event.WorkItemId  $\leftarrow$  work_item_counter
30       | work_item_counter  $\leftarrow$  work_item_counter + 1
31     end
32   end
33   return Case
```

4.4 Normative Models

A normative model represents how a process is supposed to operate according to the workflow designed by a municipality. These workflows are stored in the regulatory patterns tables that were created in the transformation step. Table 4.2 showed the attributes of the regulatory patterns.

The regulatory patterns table defines only the sequential relationships between process stages and does not specify whether subsequent stages are to be executed exclusively or in parallel, see Section 3.4. In line with the default configuration of municipal intended workflows, which are modeled using exclusive choices, the normative model generation in this section produces models without concurrency. To illustrate the generation of the normative models, the example process from Table 2.2 is used.

However, this example originally contained a parallel sequence for the three different checks following the *Assessment* process stage. To conform to typical municipal workflow design, this has been adapted to an exclusive sequence. The corresponding regulatory patterns table for the adjusted process is shown in Table 4.4.

For clarity, Table 4.4 presents a simplified representation of a regulatory patterns table. Attributes such as the process identifiers and stage descriptions are omitted, only the *ProcessStageFrom* and *ProcessStageTo* columns are shown. The section is structured as follows:

Section 4.4.1 covers the generation of a Petri Net model and Section 4.4.2 covers the generation of a BPMN model.

ProcessStageFrom	ProcessStageTo
Submit Request	Assessment
Assessment	Background Check
Assessment	Reference Check
Assessment	Credit Check
Background Check	Evaluation
Reference Check	Evaluation
Credit Check	Evaluation
Evaluation	Accept Request
Evaluation	Reject Request
Accept Request	Inform Client
Reject Request	Inform Client

Table 4.4: Simplified Regulatory Patterns of the example process.

4.4.1 Normative Petri Net Model

This subsection covers the generation of the normative Petri Net model. A Petri Net has a set of places, a set of transitions and a flow relation (Def 11). The generation of a normative Petri Net model is divided into several operations, which are detailed below:

The first operation is analyze the process stage frequencies. The regulatory pattern table has the attributes *ProcessStageFrom* and *ProcessStageTo*, which show how the different process stages in a process are connected. In order words, these attributes can be used to determine for each process stage how many time it appears as a source stage and as a target stage.

The results of this first operation are the frequencies for each process stage, which holds information about how many predecessors and successors a process stage has in the intended workflow. Table 4.5 shows the frequency table of the example process.

Process Stage	Predecessors	Successors
Submit Request	0	1
Assessment	1	3
Background Check	1	1
Reference Check	1	1
Credit Check	1	1
Evaluation	3	2
Accept Request	1	1
Reject Request	1	1
Inform Client	2	0

Table 4.5: Stage transition frequencies of the example process.

The second operation is the creation of the initial place and the output place of the petri net. The initial place is the starting point of the Petri Net with the initial marking ► and the output place is the ending of the petri net, with the final marking ■.

The third operation is the creation of the transitions. A transition is created for each unique process stage that occurs in the regulatory patterns table. The information of the process stage frequencies from the first operation can be used to determine which transition has no predecessors and which transition has no successors. The initial place is connected to the transition with no predecessors, which is the starting stage and the transition with no successors is connected to the output place, which is the ending stage. Figure 4.2a shows how the example process looks like after the third operation.

The fourth operation is the creation of the output places for the transitions. Each transition that has more than one successor, based on the process stage frequencies, is connected to a newly created output place for that transition. Figure 4.2b shows how the example process looks like after the fourth operation.

The fifth operation is to connect the transitions which have exactly one successor. The transition is connected to the place that is the input place of the successor transition. If this place does not yet exist, this input place is created for the successor transition. Figure 4.2c shows how the example process looks like after the fifth operation.

The sixth operation is to connect the transitions which have exactly one predecessor. The transition is connected to the place that is the output place of the predecessor transition, which then becomes the input place of the transition. If this place does not yet exist, the connection will be added in a later operation. Figure 4.2d shows how the example process looks like after the sixth operation.

The Petri Net generated after operation six closely resembles the model in Figure 2.1c, but models the behavior after the *Assessment* stage as an exclusive choice rather than a concurrent execution. If the *Assessment* process stage would require all three checks to be executed, instead of only one of them, a municipality would model them as a fixed sequence of events. Table 4.6 shows the regulatory patterns table with the fixed sequence of events.

(a) Petri Net generation, Operation.

(b) Petri Net generation, Operation 4.

(c) Petri Net generation, Operation 5.

(d) Petri Net generation, Operation 6.

Figure 4.2: Operation-by-operation overview of the Petri Net generation for the example process.

ProcessStageFrom	ProcessStageTo
Submit Request	Assessment
Assessment	Background Check
Background Check	Reference Check
Reference Check	Credit Check
Credit Check	Evaluation
Evaluation	Accept Request
Evaluation	Reject Request
Accept Request	Inform Client
Reject Request	Inform Client

Table 4.6: Sequential Regulatory Patterns of the example process.

Figure 4.3 shows the Petri Net model that is generated after operation six, based on the sequential regulatory patterns table of the example process.

Figure 4.3: Petri Net generated from sequential regulatory patterns for the example process.

Both models generated from the regulatory patterns tables of the example process do not include any complex patterns that require the use of silent transitions. However, by expanding the example process with an additional process stage, *Outsource Assessment*, which directly connects to the *Accept Request* and *Reject Request* stages, the resulting model becomes more complex. The expanded regulatory patterns table is shown in Table 4.7.

ProcessStageFrom	ProcessStageTo
Submit Request	Assessment
Submit Request	Outsource Assessment
Assessment	Background Check
Background Check	Reference Check
Reference Check	Credit Check
Credit Check	Evaluation
Evaluation	Accept Request
Evaluation	Reject Request
Outsource Assessment	Accept Request
Outsource Assessment	Reject Request
Accept Request	Inform Client
Reject Request	Inform Client

Table 4.7: Expanded Regulatory Patterns of the example process.

Figure 4.4a shows the expanded example process after the sixth operation. The current operations for generating the normative Petri Net model are not sufficient to produce a complete model for more complex processes. Therefore, additional operations are required to ensure the construction of a valid and complete model:

The seventh operation is to create the input places for the transitions which have no incoming place connected yet from the previous operations. These are transitions with more than one predecessor, for which none of the predecessors has exactly one successor. These transitions can not be directly linked together, and require additional 'silent' transitions, which will be added in the next operation. Figure 4.4b shows how the expanded example process looks like after the seventh operation.

The eighth operation is to create these silent transitions between all the transitions which are not yet connected, while they should be directly connected according to the regulatory patterns. The output place of the predecessor transition is connected to a newly created silent transition, and this silent transition is then connected to the input place of the successor. Figure 4.4c shows how the expanded example process looks like after the eighth operation.

(a) Petri Net generation, Operation 6.

(b) Petri Net generation, Operation 7.

(c) Petri Net generation, Operation 8.

Figure 4.4: Operation-by-operation overview of the Petri Net generation for the expanded example process.

Algorithm 12 shows in pseudo code how the normative petri nets are generated.

Algorithm 12: Generation of a Normative Petri Net (Part 1/2)

Input: *regulatory_patterns* table.

Output: Normative Petri Net \mathcal{N} .

Pre-condition : The *regulatory_patterns* table is well-formed w.r.t. the format described in Table 4.2.

Post-condition : \mathcal{N} is a Petri Net without concurrency

```
1 Function GENERATE_NORMATIVE_PETRI_NET(regulatory_pattern)
2    $\mathcal{N} \leftarrow \text{NewNet}()$  // Step 1
3   freq  $\leftarrow \text{StageFrequencies}(\textit{regulatory\_pattern})$  // Step 2
4   add NewPlace(p_initial)  $\leftarrow \mathcal{N}$ 
5   add NewPlace(p_output)  $\leftarrow \mathcal{N}$ 
6   foreach process_stage  $\in$  freq do // Step 3
7     add NewTransition(t_process_stage)  $\rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ 
8     if freq[process_stage].predecessors = 0 then
9       | add NewArc(p_initial, t_process_stage)  $\rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ 
10    end
11    if freq[process_stage].successors = 0 then
12      | add NewArc(t_process_stage, p_output)  $\rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ 
13    end
14    if freq[process_stage].successors > 1 then // Step 4
15      | add NewPlace(p_process_stage_out)  $\rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ 
16      | add NewArc(t_process_stage, p_process_stage_out)  $\rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ 
17    end
18  end
19  foreach (process_stage_from, process_stage_to)  $\in$  regulatory_pattern do // Step 5
20    if freq[process_stage_from].successors = 1 then
21      | if p_process_stage_to_in  $\in \mathcal{N}$  then
22        | add NewArc(t_process_stage_from, p_process_stage_to_in)  $\rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ 
23      | end
24      | else
25        | add NewPlace(p_process_stage_to_in)  $\rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ 
26        | add NewArc(t_process_stage_from, p_process_stage_to_in)  $\rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ 
27      | end
28    end // Step 6
29    if freq[process_stage_to].predecessors = 1 then
30      | if p_process_stage_from_out  $\in \mathcal{N}$  then
31        | add NewArc(p_process_stage_from_out, t_process_stage_to)  $\rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ 
32      | end
33    end
34  end
```

Algorithm 12: Generation of a Normative Petri Net (Part 2/2).

```
34 ..... // Step 7
35   foreach  $t\_process\_stage \in \mathcal{N}$  do
36     if not HasIncomingArc( $t\_process\_stage$ ) then
37       add NewPlace( $p\_process\_stage\_in$ )  $\rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ 
38       add NewArc( $p\_process\_stage\_in, t\_process\_stage$ )  $\rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ 
39     end
40   end // Step 8
41   foreach ( $process\_stage\_from, process\_stage\_to$ )  $\in regulatory\_pattern$  do
42     if not ArcExists( $t\_process\_stage\_from, p\_process\_stage\_to\_in$ ) and not
43       ArcExists( $p\_process\_stage\_from\_out, t\_process\_stage\_to$ ) then
44       add NewTransition( $t\_tau$ )  $\rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ 
45       add NewArc( $p\_process\_stage\_from\_out, t\_tau$ )  $\rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ 
46       add NewArc( $t\_tau, p\_process\_stage\_to\_in$ )  $\rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ 
47     end
48   end
49   return  $\mathcal{N}$ 
```

This subsection covered the generation of the normative Petri Net models. These Petri Net models are created for both the processed and raw dataset. The next subsection will cover the generation of the normative BPMN models.

4.4.2 Normative BPMN model

A BPMN has a set of nodes, which includes activities, gateways, and start/end events, and a sequence flow (Def 10). The generation of a normative BPMN model is divided into several operations, which are detailed below:

The first operation is analyzing the process stage frequencies, which is the same first operation as for the generation of the normative Petri Net models in Section 4.4.1. Table 4.5 showed the frequency table of the example process.

The second operation is the creation of the nodes that correspond to the start and end events of the model. The start event is indicated as an empty circle and the end event is indicated as an empty circle with a double border. Alternatively, the start event can be indicated as a green circle and the end event can be indicated as an orange circle.

The third operation is the creation of the nodes that correspond to the activities of the model. An activity is created for each unique process stage that occurs in the regulatory patterns table. The information of the process stage frequencies from the first operation can be used to determine which activity has no predecessors and which activity has no successors. The start event is connected to the activity with no predecessors, which is the starting stage and the activity with no successors is connected to the end event, which is the ending stage. Figure 4.5a shows how the example process looks like after the third operation.

The fourth operation is the creation of the nodes that correspond to the XOR (exclusive choice) gateways of the model. Each activity node that has more than one successor, based on the process stage frequencies, is connected to a generated XOR-split gateway. They are connected from the gateway node into the activity node. Each activity node that has more than one predecessors, based on the process stage frequencies, is connected to a generated XOR-join gateway. They are connected from the activity node into the gateway node. Figure 4.5b shows how the example process looks like after the fourth operation.

The fifth operation is connecting the XOR-split gateways of the source activity nodes to the target activity nodes that have only one predecessor. Since these target activities do not have more than one predecessors, they do not have a XOR-join gateway which should be in between the connection. They are connected from the gateway node into the target activity node. Figure 4.5c shows how the example process looks like after the fifth operation.

The sixth operation is connecting the XOR-join gateways of the target activity nodes to the source activity nodes that have only one successor. Since these source activities do not have more than one successor, they do not have a XOR-split gateway, should should be in between the connection. They are connected from the source activity node to the gateway node. Figure 4.5d shows how the example process looks like after the fourth operation.

The seventh operation is connecting the source activity nodes with one successor to the target activity nodes with one predecessor. since both the source activity and the target activity have no gateways, they can be connected together directly from the source activity to the target activity. Figure 4.5e shows how the example process looks like after the fourth operation.

The BPMN after operation seven closely resembles the model in Figure 2.1a, but models the behavior of the *Assessment* stage as an exclusive choice (XOR) rather than a parallel sequence (AND). Due to the complexity of the example process, the generated model does not require any connections between a XOR-split and a XOR-join gateway.

However, by using the expanded example process from the previous subsection which included an additional process stage *Outsource Assessment*, this connection is required. The expanded regulatory patterns table was shown in Table 4.7.

(a) BPMN generation, Operation 3.

(b) BPMN generation, Operation 4.

(c) BPMN generation, Operation 5.

(d) BPMN generation, Operation 6.

(e) BPMN generation, Operation 7.

Figure 4.5: Operation-by-operation overview of the BPMN generation for the example process.

As can be seen in Figure 4.6a, the expanded example process after the seventh operation is not completed. Therefore, an additional operation is required to ensure the construction of a valid and complete model:

The eight operation is connecting the XOR-split gateways to the XOR-join gateways. A source activity with multiple successors has a XOR-split gateway and the target activity with multiple predecessors has a XOR-join gateway, which need to be connected. Figure 4.6b shows how the expanded example process looks like after the fourth operation.

Figure 4.6: Operation-by-operation overview of the BPMN generation for the expanded example process.

Algorithm 13 shows in pseudo code how the normative BPMNs are generated.

This section covered the generation of the normative Petri Net models and the normative BPMN models. These models are created for both the processed and raw dataset. The next section will cover the automated discovery step of the framework

Algorithm 13: Generation of a Normative BPMN (Part 1/2).

Input: *regulatory_pattern* table.

Output: Normative *BPMN*.

Pre-condition : The *regulatory_patterns* table is well-formed w.r.t. the format described in Table 4.2.

Post-condition : *BPMN* is a BPMN without concurrency

```
1 Function GENERATE_NORMATIVE_BPMN(regulatory_pattern)
2   BPMN  $\leftarrow$  NewBPMN() // Step 1
3   freq  $\leftarrow$  StageFrequencies(regulatory_pattern) // Step 2
4   add NewEvent(e_start)  $\rightarrow$  BPMN
5   add NewEvent(e_end)  $\rightarrow$  BPMN
6   foreach process_stage  $\in$  keys(freq) do // Step 3
7     add NewActivity(a_process_stage)  $\rightarrow$  BPMN
8     if freq[process_stage].predecessors = 0 then
9       | add NewSequenceFlow (e_start, a_process_stage)  $\rightarrow$  BPMN
10    end
11    if freq[process_stage].successors = 0 then
12      | add NewSequenceFlow (a_process_stage, e_end)  $\rightarrow$  BPMN
13    end // Step 4
14    if freq[process_stage].successors > 1 then
15      | add NewGateway(g_process_stage_split)  $\rightarrow$  BPMN
16      | add NewSequenceFlow (a_process_stage, g_process_stage_split)  $\rightarrow$  BPMN
17    end
18    if freq[process_stage].predecessors > 1 then
19      | add NewGateway(g_process_stage_join)  $\rightarrow$  BPMN
20      | add NewSequenceFlow (g_process_stage_join, a_process_stage)  $\rightarrow$  BPMN
21    end
22  end
23  for each (process_stage_from, process_stage_to)  $\in$  regulatory_pattern do // Step 5
24    if freq[process_stage_from].successors > 1 then
25      | if freq[process_stage_to].predecessors = 1 then
26        | add NewSequenceFlow (g_process_stage_from_split, a_process_stage_to)
27        |  $\rightarrow$  BPMN
28      | end
29    end // Step 6
30    if freq[process_stage_to].predecessors > 1 then
31      | if freq[process_stage_from].successors = 1 then
32        | add NewSequenceFlow (a_process_stage_from, g_process_stage_to_join)
33        |  $\rightarrow$  BPMN
34      | end
35    end
```

Algorithm 13: Generation of a Normative BPMN (Part 2/2).

```
32 .....
33 | .....
34 | | if freq[process_stage_from].successors = 1 then // Step 7
35 | | | if freq[process_stage_to].predecessors = 1 then
36 | | | | add NewSequenceFlow (a_process_stage_from, a_process_stage_to)
37 | | | | |  $\rightarrow \mathcal{BPMN}$ 
38 | | | end
39 | | end // Step 8
40 | | if freq[process_stage_from].successors > 1 then
41 | | | if freq[process_stage_to].predecessors > 1 then
42 | | | | add NewSequenceFlow (g_process_stage_from_split,
43 | | | | | g_process_stage_to_join)  $\rightarrow \mathcal{BPMN}$ 
44 | | | end
45 | | end
46 | end
47 | return  $\mathcal{BPMN}$ 
```

4.5 Descriptive Models

Using process discovery techniques, a process model can be derived from the XES event log. The resulting model is referred to as the descriptive process model, as it represents how the process is actually executed based on the XES event log.

The automated discovery relies on the information contained in the XES event logs generated in the XES generation step. The different elements and attributes of the XES event log are explained in Section 4.3. The automated discovery of the process models is divided into several operations, which are detailed below:

The first operation of the automated discovery is to group all events in the event log that share the same *WorkItemId*, i.e., the events that belong to the same activity instance, and merge them together into a single event. For the merged event, the *StageStartDate* attribute is taken from the start event of the lifecycle transition, and the *time:timestamp* (*StageEndDate*) is taken from the final completed/terminated event of the lifecycle transition, therefore retaining the interval duration of the activity instance.

The merging prevents the event of the same activity instance from appearing multiple times in a trace of the event log, which would create an inflation of trace variants. These trace variants would reflect inaccurate and inconsistent process behavior.

Table 4.8 shows an example multiset of traces before and after the merging of the events inside of an activity instance. Each trace lists the activity labels of the events, with the lifecycle transition written as a subscript.

Before merging	After merging
$\langle a_{\text{start}}, a_{\text{complete}}, b_{\text{start}}, b_{\text{complete}}, c_{\text{start}}, c_{\text{complete}} \rangle^3$	$\langle a, b, c \rangle^6$
$\langle a_{\text{start}}, a_{\text{complete}}, b_{\text{start}}, b_{\text{suspend}}, b_{\text{resume}}, b_{\text{complete}}, c_{\text{start}}, c_{\text{complete}} \rangle^2$	$\langle a, d, c \rangle^3$
$\langle a_{\text{start}}, a_{\text{complete}}, b_{\text{start}}, b_{\text{reassign}}, b_{\text{complete}}, c_{\text{start}}, c_{\text{complete}} \rangle^1$	$\langle a, e, c \rangle^2$
$\langle a_{\text{start}}, a_{\text{complete}}, d_{\text{start}}, d_{\text{complete}}, c_{\text{start}}, c_{\text{complete}} \rangle^2$	$\langle a, b, e, c \rangle^2$
$\langle a_{\text{start}}, a_{\text{complete}}, d_{\text{start}}, d_{\text{suspend}}, d_{\text{resume}}, d_{\text{complete}}, c_{\text{start}}, c_{\text{complete}} \rangle^1$	
$\langle a_{\text{start}}, a_{\text{complete}}, e_{\text{start}}, e_{\text{complete}}, c_{\text{start}}, c_{\text{complete}} \rangle^2$	
$\langle a_{\text{start}}, a_{\text{complete}}, b_{\text{start}}, b_{\text{complete}}, e_{\text{start}}, e_{\text{complete}}, c_{\text{start}}, c_{\text{complete}} \rangle^1$	
$\langle a_{\text{start}}, a_{\text{complete}}, b_{\text{start}}, b_{\text{complete}}, e_{\text{suspend}}, e_{\text{resume}}, e_{\text{complete}}, c_{\text{start}}, c_{\text{complete}} \rangle^1$	

Table 4.8: Effect of merging events with the same *WorkItemId* on the trace variants.

In the example multiset of traces, the number of distinct variants decreases from eight before merging to four after merging. The result of the merging is a cleaner, more representative basis for discovery with fewer, more meaningful variants.

The second operation applies the merged event log to discover a process model. The discovery of the process model is done with the Inductive Miner (infrequent variant). This variant includes a noise threshold that behaves as an infrequent-behavior filter. It removes low frequency directly-follows relations and exceptional paths so the result is a sound, block-structured model that is simpler and more precise [17].

The Inductive Miner uses a noise threshold $\theta \in [0,1]$ to filter the infrequent behavior. Lower values of θ retain more of the log's behavior in the model, while higher values filter out infrequent behavior and produces a simpler but potentially less fitting model. The optimal value for θ is log-dependent and is determined for each event log empirically using the following steps:

1. A set of noise threshold values Θ is defined, which consists of values between 0 and 1, incremented by 0.05, e.g. $\{0.00, 0.05, 0.10, \dots, 1.00\}$.
2. For each $\theta \in \Theta$, discover a model M_θ using the merged event log and the noise threshold θ .
3. For each M_θ , compute the four quality criteria: fitness, precision, generalization, and simplicity (see Subsection 2.1.3 for their definitions). These metrics are obtained via conformance checking, which is covered in the next section of the framework.
4. Select the optimal threshold θ^* as follows:
 - (a) Compute the F-score for each model as the harmonic mean of fitness and precision:

$$F_{\text{score}} = 2 \times \frac{\text{fitness} \times \text{precision}}{\text{fitness} + \text{precision}}$$

This ensures that only models scoring well on both dimensions achieve a high F-score.

- (b) Identify the subset of thresholds in Θ that maximize F_{score} .
- (c) From these, select those with the highest generalization and the highest simplicity.
- (d) If multiple thresholds remain, select the lowest θ to preserve the most genuine behavior.

This optimal θ is then used to discover the final descriptive models. Each log produces both a Petri net and a BPMN model under the chosen noise setting.

This section has detailed the automated discovery of descriptive Petri Net and BPMN models for both the processed and raw datasets. The next section will address conformance checking step of the framework

4.6 Conformance Checking

Conformance checking is performed using the XES event logs, as well as the normative and descriptive process models generated in the previous steps of the framework.

As described in Section 2.1.3, conformance checking evaluates how well an event log fits a given process model by quantifying deviations between modeled and observed behavior. The two techniques that are applied in this framework are the token-based replay and alignment.

These techniques are both performed on the normative and descriptive Petri Net models in combination with the merged XES event log. BPMN models are not used here, since only petri nets provide the formal execution semantics which are needed for these techniques.

This section covers the different conformance checking techniques along with their associated quality metrics, and is structured as follows: Section 4.6.1 covers the token-based replay technique and Section 4.6.2 covers alignment technique.

4.6.1 Token-based Replay

The token-based replay technique replays each trace from the merged XES event log on both the normative and descriptive petri nets by firing transitions in the order of the observed activity instances.

During replay, each transition consumes tokens from its input places and produces tokens in its output places. Whenever a transition cannot fire due to missing tokens, those tokens are recorded as *missing*. Any tokens left in the Petri Net after replaying a trace are recorded as *remaining*. The following quality metrics can be derived from the token-based replay:

- **Fitness:** Let p be the total number of produced tokens, c the total number of consumed tokens, m the total missing tokens, and r the total remaining tokens over all traces. The fitness can be calculated with the following formula [36]:

$$\text{Fitness} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{m}{c} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{r}{p} \right).$$

which balances how many events could not fire due to missing tokens and how many tokens were left unused.

- **Precision** Precision measures the extent to which the model prohibits behavior not seen in the log. A common token-based precision estimate compares the number of enabled but unobserved transitions during replay to the total number of enabled transitions [37].
- **Generalization** Generalization measures the likelihood that the process model can describe yet-unseen behavior. It penalizes dead or rarely used parts of the model and applies diminishing returns to repeated occurrences, favoring models that cover the visible behavior without overfitting [38].
- **Simplicity** Simplicity evaluates the structural complexity of the petri net, e.g., counting the

number of places, transitions, arcs, and control-flow constructs. Simpler models, which have fewer elements, receive higher simplicity scores. This metric is log-independent and does not rely on token replay, it is computed solely from the model's structure.

4.6.2 Alignment

The alignment technique finds, for each trace in the merged XES event log, an optimal sequence of moves that aligns the observed events to transitions in a petri net.

The optimal alignment is obtained by minimizing a cost function that assigning zero or low cost to *synchronous moves* (an event matches an enabled transition) and a high cost to *log moves* (an event without matching transition) and *model moves* (a transition without a matching event) [39]. From the optimal alignment's move counts and total cost, the following quality metrics can be derived:

- **Fitness:** Let $\text{cost}^*(t)$ be the total cost of the optimal alignment of trace t with the petri net, and let $\text{cost}^\perp(t)$ be the *worst-case* cost for t , i.e., an alignment without synchronous moves. The fitness can be calculated with the following formula [40]:

$$\text{Fitness} = 1 - \frac{\sum_{t \in L} \text{cost}^*(t)}{\sum_{t \in L} \text{cost}^\perp(t)},$$

where L denotes the event log and the summations are taken over all traces $t \in L$.

- **Precision:** Precision measures how much extra behavior the model allows beyond what appears in the aligned log using *anti-alignments*. It searches for model runs that are maximally distant from the log and penalizes such enabled but unobserved behavior. The farther these anti-alignments are from the observed behavior, the lower the precision [41].
- **Generalization:** Generalization measures the likelihood that the process model can describe yet-unseen behavior via *anti-alignments*. Using a leave-one-out view, it checks if the model still produces behavior close to a removed trace, but in contrast to precision, this metric depends on the frequency of the traces. [41].
- **Simplicity** As with token replay, simplicity is derived from the structural complexity of the Petri Net and is log-independent. It is computed solely from the model's structure.

This section detailed the conformance-checking techniques and their associated quality metrics. These techniques are applied on both the processed and raw datasets. The next section will cover the process diagnostics step of the framework.

4.7 Process Diagnostics

Besides conformance checking, additional analyses can be performed to gather insights and identify deviations on the process. Together, these analyses are the final outputs of the framework, as they provide the concrete diagnostic results derived from the XES event logs and the normative and descriptive process models produced in earlier steps of the framework. This section covers the different types of analysis performed and is structured as follows:

Section 4.7.1 presents the variant analysis, Section 4.7.2 discusses the event analysis, Section 4.7.3 covers the resource analysis, Section 4.7.4 introduces the duration analysis, Section 4.7.5 examines the transition analysis, Section 4.7.6 focuses on the cycle analysis, Section 4.7.7 addresses the soundness analysis, and Section 4.7.8 concludes with the footprint analysis.

4.7.1 Variant Analysis

The variant analysis examines how the trace variants differ between the XES event log and the merged XES event log, as well as which trace variants are compatible with the discovered process model and the normative process model. The different variant analysis are detailed below:

- **Merged XES event log:** As mentioned in Section 4.5, the merging of the events of the same activity instance prevents the inflation of trace variants. This analysis shows the difference between the trace variants of the original XES log and the merged XES log.
- **Descriptive model:** The descriptive model is discovered using a noise threshold, which aims at filtering out infrequent behavior to produce a simpler process model. This analysis shows which trace variants of the event log comply with the discovered descriptive model and which trace variants are excluded.
- **Normative model:** The normative model is the intended workflow designed by the municipality. This analysis shows which trace variants of the event log comply with the normative model, as well as comparing these trace variants with the trace variants that are allowed by the descriptive model.

4.7.2 Event Analysis

The event analysis examines the individual events within the process, for both the XES event log and the merged XES event log. The different event analysis are detailed below:

- **Start activities:** Identifying which events initiate cases, including their frequency.
- **End activities:** Identifying which events close cases, including their frequency.
- **Overall event frequencies:** Examines the frequency the process stage of each event that occurs in the process.
- **Lifecycle frequencies:** Examines the frequency of the lifecycle transitions of each event that occurs in the process.

4.7.3 Resource Analysis

The resource analysis examines which resources are used within the process, for both the XES event log and the merged XES event log. The different employees and teams that are responsible for the cases and events. The different resource analysis are detailed below:

- **Team frequencies:** Examines the frequency of the team that is responsible for each event that occurs in the process.
- **Employee frequencies:** Examines the frequency of the employee that is responsible for each event that occurs in the process.
- **Resource frequencies:** Examines the frequency of the combination of a team and employee that is responsible for each event that occurs in the process.

4.7.4 Duration Analysis

The duration analysis examines the case duration of the different cases within a XES event log. The different duration analysis are detailed below:

- **Total case duration:** The total duration of all the cases of the process.
- **Median case duration:** The median duration of the cases of the process.

- **Case duration:** The case duration for each individual case of the process.
- **Case duration frequencies:** Examines the frequency of the different case durations of the process. This information is used to build a histogram of case durations and the KDE plot.
- **Variant case duration:** The total and the median duration of the trace variants.

4.7.5 Transition Analysis

The transition analysis compares the descriptive and normative model transitions and connections. The different transition analysis are detailed below:

- **Transition succession:** Identifying for each transition of a model what the succession transitions are, and comparing if a transition has the same successors in both models or what the differences are.
- **Transition presence:** Identifying the difference between what transitions appear only in the normative or in the descriptive model.

4.7.6 Cycle Analysis

The cycle analysis examines whether there are cycles in the normative and descriptive models and compares the models to see if the cycles are present in both. A cycle is a loop, where the process model allows a sequence of activities to return to an earlier activity, potentially repeating. The different cycle analyses are detailed below:

- **Cycle detection:** Identifies every cycle that exists in a process model.
- **Cycle overlap:** Shows the cycles that are present in both the normative and descriptive models.
- **Cycle frequency:** Examines if the cycles are present in the XES event log and their frequency.

4.7.7 Soundness Analysis

The soundness analysis examines whether the normative and descriptive models are behaviorally well-formed. In particular, a sound process model should be free of dead transitions, livelocks, and deadlocks, and it should guarantee proper completion.

4.7.8 Footprint Analysis

Footprint analysis evaluates the differences between the normative and descriptive models by transforming their control-flow relations, causal, parallel, and exclusive, into footprint matrices. Each entry in the matrix indicates how two activities relate to one another. By comparing the two matrices, discrepancies between the normative and the descriptive model behavior can be identified:

- **Causal mismatches:** A causal mismatch occurs when one model allows activity A to precede activity B, while the other model does not allow this.
- **Parallel mismatches:** A parallel mismatch occurs when one model allows both activity A to precede activity B and activity B to precede activity A (i.e., the activities are in parallel), while the other model does not allow this.
- **Exclusive mismatches:** An exclusive mismatch occurs when one model does not allow activity A and activity B to follow one another (i.e., they are mutually exclusive), while the other model does.

This chapter introduced the municipal process analysis framework and detailed each of its components, from data preprocessing and transformation through the generation of XES event logs, normative and descriptive models, and the subsequent conformance checking and process diagnostics. The next chapter presents the implementation of the framework.

5 Implementation and Case Studies

This chapter explains the practical implementation of the structural framework designed in Chapter 4 and demonstrates its application on municipal process data. The chapter is structured as follows:

Section 5.1 outlines the concrete implementation choices of the framework and Section 5.2 presents two case studies, based on datasets from different municipalities.

5.1 Implementation

This section describes the practical implementation of the framework, covering the programming language and libraries used, how the overall code base is structured, and the file formats used for the data and models. The section addresses the different aspects of the implementation in detail and is structured as follows:

Section 5.1.1 introduces the programming language and libraries, Section 5.1.2 details the code structure, Section 5.1.3 explains the file formats, and Section 5.1.4 provides the implementation repository.

5.1.1 Programming Language and Libraries

The programming language that is used for the implementation of the framework is Python, which is a dynamic, high-level language designed with an emphasis on code readability. Python is widely used for data analysis and its extensive ecosystem of libraries cover the framework's needs, making it a well-suited choice for this implementation.

There are several different libraries used in the implementation of this framework. Table 5.1 lists the key Python libraries used in the implementation of the framework.

Library	Role	Description
PM4Py [42]	Process mining	Provides core process-mining capabilities, including data structures for process trees, Petri nets, BPMN models and XES event logs and algorithms for process discovery, conformance checking, and process analysis.
Pandas [43]	Data processing	Handles tabular data, enabling efficient reading and writing of data files, joining and merging data frames, and reshaping data to match the structure required for process mining.
NumPy [44]	Numerical computing	Performs efficient numerical calculations, enabling fast vectorized operations for aggregations, statistical measures, and other performance-critical computations on large datasets.

Table 5.1: Python libraries used in the framework implementation.

The implementation of the framework uses PM4Py for the process-mining functions and data structures, while Pandas and NumPy provide the required data processing and numerical capabilities.

This subsection covered the programming language and libraries used. The next subsection covers the code structure of the implementation.

5.1.2 Code Structure

The implementation of the framework follows a modular structure, allowing each framework step to be executed independently or as part of a complete end-to-end pipeline. An overview of the code structure is shown in Figure 5.1.

Figure 5.1: Overview of the framework’s code structure

The *src/* directory contains the main components for each framework step, which includes the preprocessing (*data_preprocessing.py*, Section 4.1), transformation (*data_transformation.py*, Section 4.2), visualization (*data_visualization.py*), pre-selection (*data_pre_selection.py*), XES event log generation (*xes_generation.py*, Section 4.3), normative model generation (*process_generation.py*, Section 4.4), and descriptive model discovery (*process_discovery.py*, Section 4.5).

The pre-selection and visualization steps are not described in the framework design from Chapter 4, as they are optional components that proved useful during development but are not essential to the framework's operation. The pre-selection component is optionally executed after the transformation step (see Section 4.2) and the visualization component is optionally executed after the XES generation step (see Section 4.3).

The pre-selection component filters the number of processes from the dataset that are used for the later steps of the framework. Large municipal datasets can contain information on hundreds of distinct processes, some of which have only a few recorded cases. In addition, certain processes consist of a low number of process stages and paths between them, resulting in very small and simple models. To address this, the pre-selection step compares the number of cases, events, and process stages for each process in the event log and the number of paths in the regulatory patterns, retaining only those processes with sufficient data and structural complexity.

The visualization component generates a directly-follows graph (DFG) for each regulatory patterns table, providing an initial impression of the process structure and complexity.

The *mappings/* directory contains configuration files for the data, including translations for the descriptive attributes, dataset time frames, and the calculated noise thresholds for the individual processes. These configurations are required by various framework components. However, when a new dataset is added, the corresponding configuration files must be manually updated to include its configurations. Otherwise, the components will revert to default values for that dataset.

The *data/* directory stores all intermediate and final outputs of the framework, organized into sub folders corresponding to the different processing steps. It contains the data produced after each step, as well as the exported Petri Net models, BPMN models, XES event logs, visualizations, and diagnostics results.

The top level includes scripts that coordinate execution and provide shared utilities. The *utils.py* and *process_mining_utils.py* scripts contain helper functions used across multiple framework components. The *pipeline.py* script is the main executable of the framework. It coordinates the sequential execution of the different components of the framework. Finally, the *analysis.py* script implements the different process diagnostics functions.

This subsection covered the code structure of the framework implementation. The next subsection introduces the file formats used for storing the data and for providing input to the framework.

5.1.3 File Formats

The municipal datasets are provided as multiple `.csv` files, with each file representing a different database table (see Section 3.2 for an overview of these tables). As described in Chapter 4, the private steps of the framework filter these extracted `.csv` files to retain only relevant tables and attributes, apply anonymization and generalization. These are then converted to `.parquet` format to serve as the input for the public components of the implementation and are stored in the `generalized_data/` directory.

All intermediate and final outputs are stored in their respective subfolders, primarily in `.parquet` format. However, Petri nets models are exported as `.pnml` files, BPMN models as `.bpmn` files, XES event logs as `.xes` files, and visualizations as `.png` images.

5.1.4 Repository

The full implementation of the framework, including all source code, configuration files, data files, and instructions for execution, is available in the public repository on [GitLab](#) or on [Zenodo](#) [45].

The source code provides the actual implementation of the pseudo code described in Chapter 4, as well as the concrete use of external libraries and their functionalities across the different components of the framework.

The repository includes a `requirements.txt` file as well, specifying the exact Python libraries and versions required to execute the framework.

This section detailed the practical implementation of the framework. The following section applies this implementation to two municipal process datasets, illustrating how the framework operates in practice

5.2 Case Studies

The case studies are conducted on the two municipal datasets that are provided. Each case study begins with a data overview, followed by an application of the framework on the dataset. The section addresses both datasets in detail and is structured as follows:

Section 5.2.1 discusses the first case study in depth, with a step-by-step walkthrough of how the framework is applied on the dataset and how the output of the different steps are stored. For the later framework steps, a single process from the dataset is used as an example, as all other processes are handled in the same way. Section 5.2.2 describes the second case study more briefly, as applying the framework on this dataset is similar to the first case study. The main focus of this case study lies in the differences between the two datasets, thereby providing additional validation of the framework.

5.2.1 Municipality A

The first case study applies the implemented framework on the raw process data that is provided by Municipality A.

This raw process data is stored in the sub folder *municipality_A* within the *generalized_data* directory of the framework, ensuring consistent and organized data management. The same sub folder structure is used across all directories of the framework’s data directory, keeping the data of each municipality clearly separated and consistently organized.

The structure of the dataset follows the general municipal process data structure introduced in Chapter 3, with the different data tables capturing all cases, events, their attributes and descriptions, and the intended workflows of the processes.

A summary of the main characteristics of the dataset is provided in Table 5.2. The table reports the time frame of the data and the number of cases, events, laws, categories, and subcategories that are present in the dataset. Additionally, it reports the distribution of the finished, canceled, started and new cases.

Timeframe	01-01-2020 to 31-12-2023
Number of Cases	133776
Number of Events	412072
Number of Laws	1
Number of Categories	119
Number of Subcategories	5
Number of Finished Cases	129220
Number of Canceled Cases	3
Number of Started Cases	1379
Number of New Cases	3174

Table 5.2: Overview of the dataset (Municipality A).

The summary shows that the dataset consists of a single law, which is the Participation Law, covering 119 categories and 5 subcategories. The data volume is substantial, with more than 130,000 recorded cases and over 400,000 associated events spanning a four-year period, the majority of which are finished cases.

Extracting the data related to the Participation Law was a deliberate choice made in consultation with domain experts. This law is one of the most important within the social domain, and its associated processes are particularly critical to be executed efficiently. Its scale and data availability further make it a well-suited use case for applying the framework.

This part covered the data overview of municipality A. The next part will detail the effect of the preprocessing operations on the dataset.

5.2.1.1 Preprocessing

The preprocessing step refines the raw dataset to improve the quality of the data and cleans unnecessary and inaccurate data records. All preprocessing operations are applied sequentially to the Municipality A dataset, resulting in the processed dataset.

Table 5.3 reports the resulting number of cases and events after each preprocessing operation, along with the relative percentage change compared to the previous state of the dataset.

Operation	Cases	% change	Events	% change
Initial	133,776	–	412,072	–
Filter finished processes instances (4.1.2.1)	129,220	-3.41%	409,971	-0.51%
Filter early processes instances (4.1.2.2)	129,005	-0.17%	409,409	-0.14%
Filter invalid end dates (4.1.2.3)	128,900	-0.08%	409,073	-0.08%
Filter undefined process stages (4.1.2.4)	128,900	+0.00%	388,031	-5.14%
Filter missing closing stages (4.1.2.5)	106,175	-17.63%	387,865	-0.04%
Filter misclassified events (4.1.2.6)	106,175	+0.00%	385,660	-0.57%
Create start stages (4.1.2.7)	106,175	+0.00%	491,835	+27.53%

Table 5.3: Case and event count changes during preprocessing (Municipality A)

While most preprocessing operations are straightforward, as their purpose was already described in Section 4.1, a few operations either reveal important characteristics of the dataset or serve as critical validation checks.

The first preprocessing operation filtered out all unfinished cases, leaving only the finished cases. As shown in Table 5.2 in the previous subsection, the dataset initially contained 133,776 cases of which 129,220 were finished. After this operation, the number of remaining cases aligns exactly with that count, ensuring that only completed processes are considered in the subsequent operations.

The second preprocessing operation filtered out all the cases that started before the specified time frame, which for this dataset was 01-01-2020, as shown in Table 5.2. Only a small number of cases were removed, but this ensured that all recorded events belonged to cases contained in the dataset.

The fifth preprocessing operation filtered out all cases that were marked as finished but lacked a closing stage. This affected 17.63% of the cases, yet only 0.04% of the events were removed. This indicates that most of these cases contained no associated events at all, despite being flagged as finished.

Further investigation revealed that these removals were concentrated in a few specific processes rather than being evenly distributed across the dataset. In consultation with domain experts, the exact reason why these processes contain almost no recorded events remains unclear, but it may stem from issues in the underlying system affecting these particular processes. However, a detailed

investigation of the cause of this issue is beyond the scope of this thesis.

The seventh preprocessing operation added artificial start events to all cases that lacked a clearly defined starting stage. Since the number of added start events equals the total number of remaining cases, it can be concluded that the municipality has not defined a consistent starting stage for its process workflows, an issue noted in Section 4.1.1. To address this, the regulatory patterns of municipality A were preprocessed to introduce artificial start stages into the workflows of each process.

Now that both a raw and a processed dataset have been established for Municipality A, two final preprocessing operations remain to be applied on both. These operations do not remove or add cases or events but instead enrich the data with additional attributes: Operation 4.1.2.8 assigns lifecycle transitions to the events, and Operation 4.1.2.9 assigns unique identifiers to both cases and events.

Table 5.4 presents the distribution of lifecycle transitions assigned to events for both the raw and processed datasets of Municipality A.

Lifecycle Transition	Raw count	Raw %	Processed count	Processed %
complete	365,119	88.63%	446,059	90.66%
start	41,958	10.18%	41,312	8.40%
reassign	3,281	0.80%	3,220	0.65%
terminate	1,236	0.30%	868	0.18%
resume	258	0.06%	205	0.04%
suspend	158	0.04%	144	0.03%
continue	62	0.02%	27	0.01%
Total	412,072	100%	491,835	100%

Table 5.4: Lifecycle transition distribution in the raw and processed datasets (Municipality A)

In the preprocessing operations, a small number of events were removed, which explains the small differences in distribution between the raw and processed datasets. The only significant change in distribution is observed in the “complete” lifecycle. This increase is primarily the result of the artificial start stages introduced during preprocessing, as these stages are always assigned a “complete” transition and never receive any other lifecycle transition.

The raw and processed datasets are both stored in dedicated sub folders within the *processed_data/municipality_A* directory of the framework, ensuring a clear separation between them while keeping all data for Municipality A organized together.

This part detailed the effect of the preprocessing operations on the data from municipality A. The next part discusses the outcomes of the transformation step for both the raw and processed datasets, followed by the pre-selection step.

5.2.1.2 Transformation and Pre-selection

The transformation step combines all tables of the dataset into the event log and regulatory patterns, following the operations described in Section 4.2. These operations are applied to both the raw and processed datasets, which are then stored in separate sub folders within the *transformed_data/municipality_A* directory of the framework.

The event log and regulatory patterns are then partitioned into sub-event logs and sub-regulatory patterns, based on the process identifiers (Post. 14.1). The resulting partitions are stored in dedicated sub folders within the *grouped_data/municipality_A* directory of the framework.

Due to the large number of distinct processes within the datasets of Municipality A, the pre-selection component is applied to reduce the scope to those processes that provide meaningful input for the subsequent framework steps, as many processes contain only a limited number of cases and events or consist of very few stages. Nevertheless, the framework can also be executed on all processes if a broader scope of analysis is required.

The pre-selection step evaluates each process on four dimensions:

- the number of possible paths in the regulatory patterns,
- the number of unique cases in the event log,
- the number of unique events in the event log,
- the number of unique stages in the event log.

Only those processes that meet or exceed the 75th-percentile threshold for all four dimensions are retained for further analysis. The descriptive statistics used for this filtering in Municipality A are reported for both the processed dataset, see Table 5.5 and the raw dataset, see Table 5.6.

Statistic	Possible Paths	Unique Cases	Unique Events	Unique Stages
Min	2	1	4	3
25%	2	28	121	3
50%	4	210	790	4
75%	14	1061	3858	7
Max	26	7980	36621	10

Table 5.5: Descriptive statistics for process pre-selection in the processed dataset (Municipality A).

Statistic	Possible Paths	Unique Cases	Unique Events	Unique Stages
Min	1	1	3	1
25%	1	24	83	2
50%	3	182	587	3
75%	13	1046	2839	6
Max	25	12162	28689	9

Table 5.6: Descriptive statistics for process pre-selection in the raw dataset (Municipality A).

Applying this filtering operation on both the raw and processed datasets resulted in the same set of twelve processes being retained. Figure 5.2 compares these processes across the four dimensions, showing the differences in counts between the raw and processed datasets.

Figure 5.2: Comparison of pre-selected processes in the raw and processed datasets across four dimensions (Municipality A).

The selected processes show an increase in the number of possible paths (Fig. 5.2a), unique events (Fig. 5.2c), and unique stages (Fig. 5.2d) in the processed dataset, which is mainly the result of the artificial starting stages introduced during preprocessing.

At the same time, the number of cases decreases in the processed dataset (Fig. 5.2b), which is due to the filtering of cases during preprocessing. The process *0_36_2* shows a particularly large reduction, as it is one of the few processes affected by the issue described in the previous section. These processes had a large number of cases that were marked as finished but lacked a closing stage, and were therefore removed.

Table 5.7 maps the selected process identifiers to their descriptions. Since all processes fall under the *Participation Law*, only the categories and subcategories are explicitly reported.

Identifier	Category	Sub Category	Identifier	Category	Sub Category
0_02_6	Application BB	Incidental and periodic special	0_89_3	First-time income	Periodic general + special
0_MO_4	Support notification	Incidental	0_41_1	HC prior provision	Periodic general
0_90_1	Termination PW-I	Periodic general	0_77_3	Investigation into third-party payments	Periodic general + special
0_86_6	Application BB Digi-D	Incidental and periodic special	0_42_1	HC living condition	Periodic general
0_73_3	Investigation into prior provision	Periodic general + special	0_58_3	Investigation into living condition	Periodic general + special
0_36_2	Reassessment BB	Periodic special	0_ML_4	Notification	Incidental

Table 5.7: Process identifiers to descriptive names mapping for selected processes (Municipality A).

The event logs and regulatory patterns of the selected processes are stored in dedicated sub folders within the *selected_data/municipality_A* directory of the framework.

Additionally, the XES event logs are generated for the selected processes to provide the input required for the subsequent framework steps. These files are stored in the *xes_data/municipality_A* directory of the framework.

Although twelve processes were selected and continued through the framework, this case study will focus on only one of these processes in detail for the subsequent framework steps. The corresponding data and analysis results for the remaining eleven processes are available in the project repository (Section 5.1.4).

The selected process that will be detailed is *0_02_6*. This process was chosen because it has the highest number of cases and a sufficient number of events corresponding to those cases, while at the same time not being the most complex in terms of the possible paths and number of unique process stages.

This balance makes it a suitable and representative example for the case study, as it is large enough to provide meaningful insights, yet not too complex to obscure the explanation of the subsequent framework steps and the diagnostic results.

This part discussed the outcomes of the transformation step for both the raw and processed datasets, followed by the pre-selection step. The next part introduces the visualizations of the models that are generated and discovered for the detailed process *0_02_6*.

5.2.1.3 Process Models

The optional visualization step produces a directly-follows graph (Def. 9) from the regulatory patterns. This provides an initial impression of the intended process structure and complexity, which can then be compared against the generated normative models to assess their correctness.

Figure 5.3 shows the directly-follows graphs for process *0_02_6*, derived from both the raw and processed regulatory patterns.

The notable difference between the two graphs is that the raw version suggests two possible starting points, whereas the processed version introduced the artificial start stage to enforce a single entry point. Apart from this structural difference, both graphs show that possible loops are present, indicating that certain process stages can repeat after each other multiple times within a case, which contributes to the overall complexity of the process.

The raw and processed visualizations are stored in dedicated sub folders within the *visualized_data/municipality_A* directory of the framework.

The normative model generation operations produces a Petri Net (Def. 11) and a BPMN model (Def. 10) for both the raw and the processed regulatory patterns.

Since both normative models are derived from the same regulatory patterns table, their structures, process stages, and flows are expected to align with one another, as well as with the directly-follows graphs previously created. While the representations differ in syntax and modeling formalism, they should reflect the same underlying process logic.

Figures 5.4 and 5.5 shows the normative Petri Net and BPMN models derived from both the raw and processed regulatory patterns for process *0_02_6*. The BPMN visualizations were manually recreated, as the automatically generated ones did not provide a sufficiently clear or readable visualization.

The structures of the Petri Nets and BPMNs are consistent with the directly-follows graphs, as they capture the same process stages and flows in both the raw and processed versions. In both models, several loops are visible, indicating that certain stages may repeat multiple times within a case. This behavior aligns with the patterns already observed in the DFGs.

This consistency across the DFGs, Petri Nets, and BPMNs indicates that the normative models are correctly generated from the regulatory patterns table, as all three representations capture the same structure, process stages, and flows.

The raw and processed normative Petri nets and BPMNs models are stored in the framework in the *petri_data/normative/municipality_A* and *bpmn_data/normative/municipality_A* directories, respectively.

(a) Directly-Follows Graph of the raw process.

(b) Directly-Follows Graph of the processed process.

Figure 5.3: Directly-Follows Graphs for process 0_02_6.

(a) Normative Petri Net of the raw process.

(b) Normative Petri Net of the processed process.

Figure 5.4: Normative Petri Nets for process 0_02_6.

(a) Normative BPMN of the raw process.

(b) Normative BPMN of the processed process.

Figure 5.5: Normative BPMNs for process 0_02_6.

The descriptive model discovery operations produces a Petri Net (Def. 11) and a BPMN model (Def. 10) derived from both the raw and the processed XES event logs.

The discovery of the descriptive models uses the merged XES event logs and the Inductive Miner, which requires the specification of a noise threshold parameter θ . The optimal value of θ is determined by the stepwise procedure outlined in Section 4.5.

Figure 5.6 shows the quality metrics for process 0_02_6 across all evaluated noise thresholds, showing how fitness, precision, F-score, generalization, and simplicity vary with θ for both the token-based replay and alignment conformance checking algorithms.

The optimal noise threshold value for both the raw and processed models is $\theta = 0.10$, as this provides the best trade-off between the quality criteria. At this threshold, the models achieve a balanced combination of fitness and precision, resulting in the highest F-score, while also maintaining higher levels of generalization and simplicity compared to other high F-score noise thresholds.

(a) Alignments quality metrics for the raw process.

(b) Token-Based Replay quality metrics for the raw process.

(c) Alignments quality metrics for the processed process.

(d) Token-Based Replay quality metrics for the processed process.

Figure 5.6: Quality metrics for process 0_02_6 under varying noise thresholds.

Figures 5.7 and 5.8 show the descriptive Petri Net and BPMN models discovered using the optimal threshold θ and both the raw and processed merged XES event logs for process *0_02_6*.

A comparison of the raw and processed descriptive models shows that they share a largely similar structure and flow, with the main difference being the additional artificial starting stage in the processed models, which is expected.

However, the introduction of the artificial starting stage appears to have resulted in a parallel split at the beginning of the process models, indicated by a silent transition with two outgoing places for the Petri Net and as an AND-gate for the BPMN.

Unlike the regulatory patterns, which only prescribe exclusive choices, the Inductive Miner derives its structure directly from the event log and is therefore not bound by the same constraints as the normative models.

Municipal process workflows are generally designed to rely on exclusive rather than parallel choices, which makes the presence of this parallel behavior unexpected from a regulatory perspective. The following chapter will examine these descriptive models in more detail, offering deeper insights into the origins and implications of such deviations.

The raw and processed descriptive Petri nets and BPMNs models are stored in the framework under the *petri_data/descriptive/municipality_A* and *bpmn_data/descriptive/municipality_A* directories, respectively.

This part presented the results of the visualization, normative model generation, and descriptive model discovery framework steps. The next part addresses the conformance checking of the normative and descriptive models.

(a) Descriptive Petri Net of the raw process.

(b) Descriptive Petri Net of the processed process.

Figure 5.7: Descriptive Petri Nets for process 0_02_6.

(a) Descriptive BPMN of the raw process.

(b) Descriptive BPMN of the processed process.

Figure 5.8: Descriptive BPMNs for process 0_02_6.

5.2.1.4 Conformance checking

The conformance checking step uses the normative and descriptive models together with the merged XES event logs to evaluate how well the event log fits the given process models.

Table 5.8 show the result of the token-based replay and alignment techniques on both the raw and processed normative and descriptive models of process 0_02_6.

Model	Technique	Process	Fitness	Precision	F-score	Generalization	Simplicity	Cost
Normative	Token Replay	Raw	0.871	0.649	0.744	0.620	0.714	–
		Processed	0.890	0.728	0.801	0.632	0.727	–
	Alignment	Raw	0.872	0.649	0.744	–	0.714	8835.38
		Processed	0.903	0.728	0.806	–	0.727	8691.60
Descriptive	Token Replay	Raw	0.988	0.975	0.981	0.807	0.733	–
		Processed	0.990	0.960	0.975	0.848	0.756	–
	Alignment	Raw	0.983	0.975	0.979	–	0.733	1182.69
		Processed	0.989	0.960	0.974	–	0.756	975.77

Table 5.8: Conformance checking metrics for the normative and descriptive models of process 0_02_6.

Table 5.8 highlights clear differences between the normative and descriptive models.

The descriptive models achieve high fitness and precision values (0.96 - 0.99), for both the token-based replay and alignment. This indicates that the discovered models are both accurate and robust in capturing the event log behavior.

In contrast, the normative models perform noticeably lower results, especially in terms of fitness (0.87 - 0.90), and precision (0.65 - 0.73). This indicates that the regulatory patterns, while structurally correct, allow for behavior that is not reflected in the actual event logs. The substantially higher alignment costs of the normative models further show that many deviations arise when event log traces are compared to the regulatory patterns.

The comparison between the raw and processed models reveal only minor differences. The processed models generally improve the results slightly, thus showing that the preprocessing operations removed inconsistencies from the data.

Overall, the results suggests that the descriptive models fit the event data more closely, indicating that there is a gap between the regulatory patterns en the actual execution of the process.

Besides these results from the conformance checking, the framework has an additional process diagnostics step, from which more insights can be gained. The results of the process diagnostics step will be shown and discussed in Chapter 6.

The token-based replay and alignment results for both the raw and processed normative and descriptive models are stored in the framework in the *analysis_data/conformance/municipality_A* directory.

This subsection covered the first case study in detail. The following subsection describes the second case study more briefly by highlighting the differences and providing further validation of the framework.

5.2.2 Municipality B

The second case study applies the implemented framework on the raw process data that is provided by Municipality B.

The data is stored in the same way as described for Municipality A in the first case study, with the only difference being that the files are placed in the sub folder *municipality_B* for all the data directories. As this follows the same conventions, the storage details will not be repeated in this subsection.

The structure of the dataset follows the general municipal process data structure introduced in Chapter 3, with the different data tables capturing all cases, events, their attributes and descriptions, and the intended workflows of the processes.

A summary of the main characteristics of the dataset is provided in Table 5.9. The table reports the time frame of the data and the number of cases, events, laws, categories, and subcategories that are present in the dataset. Additionally, it reports the distribution of the finished, canceled, started and new cases.

Timeframe	01-01-2014 to 30-06-2016
Number of Cases	35155
Number of Events	167639
Number of Laws	1
Number of Categories	5
Number of Subcategories	3
Number of Finished Cases	34176
Number of Canceled Cases	903
Number of Started Cases	32
Number of New Cases	44

Table 5.9: Overview of the dataset (Municipality B)

The summary shows that the dataset consists of a single law, the Participation Law, covering 5 categories and 3 subcategories. The dataset is considerably smaller than that of Municipality A, with just over 35,000 recorded cases and 165,000 associated events spanning a two-and-a-half-year period, the majority of which are finished cases.

Extracting the data related to the Participation Law was a deliberate choice made in consultation with domain experts. This law is one of the most important within the social domain, and its associated processes are particularly critical to be executed efficiently.

Although smaller in scale compared to Municipality A, this dataset is particularly useful for demonstrating how the individual framework steps perform under a different dataset and for observing the differences between the two datasets.

This part covered the data overview of municipality B. The next part will detail the effect of the preprocessing operations on the dataset.

5.2.2.1 Preprocessing

The preprocessing step refines the raw dataset to improve the quality of the data and cleans unnecessary and inaccurate data records. All preprocessing operations are applied sequentially to the Municipality B dataset, resulting in the processed dataset.

Table 5.10 reports the resulting number of cases and events after each preprocessing operation, along with the relative percentage change compared to the previous state of the dataset.

Step	Cases	% change	Events	% change
Initial	35,155	–	167,639	–
Filter finished processes instances (4.1.2.1)	34,176	-2.78%	165,841	-1.07%
Filter early processes instances (4.1.2.2)	34,176	+0.00%	165,841	+0.00%
Filter invalid end dates (4.1.2.3)	34,111	-0.19%	165,590	-0.15%
Filter undefined process stages (4.1.2.4)	34,111	+0.00%	165,245	-0.21%
Filter missing closing stages (4.1.2.5)	33,558	-1.62%	164,139	-0.67%
Filter misclassified events (4.1.2.6)	33,558	+0.00%	164,139	+0.00%
Create start stages (4.1.2.7)	33,558	+0.00%	174,054	+6.04%

Table 5.10: Case and event count changes during preprocessing (Municipality B).

While most preprocessing operations are straightforward, as their purpose was already described in Section 4.1, a few operations either reveal important characteristics of the dataset or serve as critical validation checks.

The first preprocessing operation filtered out all unfinished cases, leaving only the finished cases. As shown in Table 5.9 in the previous subsection, the dataset initially contained 35,155 cases of which 34,176 were finished. After this operation, the number of remaining cases aligns exactly with that count, ensuring that only completed processes are considered in the subsequent operations.

The seventh preprocessing operation introduced artificial start events for cases that lacked a clearly defined starting stage. Since the number of artificial starts added is relatively small compared to

the total number of cases, it can be concluded that the municipality has defined a proper starting stage for its workflows.

Nevertheless, the presence of some cases without a recorded start stage indicates inconsistencies in the data. According to domain experts, this can occur when processes are initiated outside of the standard digital channels. For example, cases started online always generate a starting stage, but when initiated in person or through alternative methods, the starting stage may not be consistently registered in the system. As a result, such cases begin with an alternative stage, requiring the artificial start event to be added to ensure consistency across traces.

Now that both a raw and a processed dataset have been established for Municipality A, two final preprocessing operations remain to be applied to both. These operations do not remove or add cases or events but instead enrich the data with additional attributes: Operation 4.1.2.8 assigns lifecycle transitions to the events, and Operation 4.1.2.9 assigns unique identifiers to both cases and events.

Table 5.11 presents the distribution of lifecycle transitions assigned to events for both the raw and processed datasets of Municipality B.

Lifecycle Transition	Raw count	Raw %	Processed count	Processed %
complete	156,233	93.18%	162,753	93.49%
start	8,432	5.03%	8,335	4.79%
reassign	1,786	1.06%	1,748	1.00%
terminate	1,072	0.64%	1,102	0.63%
suspend	87	0.05%	88	0.05%
resume	23	0.01%	21	0.01%
continue	6	0.00%	7	0.00%
Total	167,639	100%	174,054	100%

Table 5.11: Lifecycle transition distribution in raw and processed datasets (Municipality B).

In the preprocessing operations, a small number of events were removed, which explains the small differences in distribution between the raw and processed datasets. As this municipality generally already had the starting stages in the cases, the "complete" lifecycle transition only increases marginally,

This part detailed the effect of the preprocessing operations on the data from municipality A. The next part discusses the outcomes of the transformation step for both the raw and processed datasets.

5.2.2.2 Transformation and Pre-selection

The transformation step combines all tables of the dataset into the event log and regulatory patterns, following the operations described in Section 4.2. These operations are applied to both

the raw and processed datasets. The event log and regulatory patterns are then partitioned into sub-event logs and sub-regulatory patterns, based on the process identifiers (Post. 14.1).

Due to the small number of distinct processes within the datasets of Municipality A, the pre-selection component is not applied and the framework is executed on all processes within this dataset.

Figure 5.9 compares these processes across the four dimensions, showing the differences in counts between the raw and processed datasets.

Figure 5.9: Comparison of processes in the raw and processed datasets across four dimensions (Municipality B).

In the processed dataset, some processes show an increase in the number of possible paths (Fig.5.9a). This increase is caused by the issue described in Section 4.1.1. Although the workflows have a clearly defined starting stage, as reflected by the unchanged number of stages (Fig. 5.9d), certain process stages cannot be reached from the starting stage through any valid path. The starting stage was connected to these unreachable process stages in the preprocessing of the regulatory patterns.

The number of unique events (Fig. 5.9c) shows both decreases and increases in the processed dataset. Decreases result from the removal of invalid or redundant events during preprocessing, while increases result from the addition of missing starting stages.

Finally, the number of cases decreases in the processed dataset (Fig. 5.9b), as incomplete or invalid cases were filtered out during preprocessing.

Compared to selected processes from Municipality A (Fig. 5.2), Municipality B contains fewer processes, but they are more complex, with a higher average number of possible paths and unique process stages. This difference arises from the fact that municipalities are free to design their own workflows and determine the number of different events that can be carried out.

Table 5.12 maps the selected process identifiers to their descriptions. Since all processes fall under the *Participation Law*, only the categories and subcategories are explicitly reported.

Identifier	Category	Sub Category
0_12_2	Application Individual Income Allowance	Periodic special
0_30_1	Maintenance Self-employed	Periodic general
0_A1_1	Application Pwet	Periodic general
0_AB_6	Application Special Assistance	Incidental and periodic special
0_O1_1	Maintenance Pwet	Periodic general

Table 5.12: Process identifiers to descriptive names mapping for selected processes in Municipality B.

The remaining steps of the framework have already been demonstrated in detail in the first case study using an example process from Municipality A. The differences between the two municipalities lie mainly in the preprocessing and transformation steps. As the subsequent framework steps are performed similarly and the data they generate is process-specific, a detailed analysis of a single process from Municipality B would not provide additional insights into the functioning of the framework. The data and analyses for the processes of Municipality B are available in the project repository (see Section 5.1.4).

This chapter described the practical implementation of the structural framework and demonstrated its application on two municipal datasets. The next chapter presents the results of the frameworks process diagnostics in detail.

6 Process Diagnosis

This chapter presents the diagnostic results produced by the framework’s process diagnostics step. These results represent the final outputs of the framework, providing insights into the process while highlighting key aspects of their behavior and uncovering deviations.

The process diagnostics are applied to each individual process that passes through the framework, making use of the corresponding XES files as well as the normative and descriptive models that are generated in the earlier steps of the framework.

To demonstrate the different types of analyses described in Section 4.7, this chapter uses the selected example process from Municipality A, introduced in Section 5.2.1, as a running example. The analysis is shown mainly for the processed dataset of the selected example process, with a few exceptions where comparisons with the raw dataset are included. The complete results for the raw dataset and for all other processes are available in the project repository. The chapter covers the results of the different types of analysis performed and is structured as follows:

Section 6.1 presents the variant analysis, Section 6.2 the event distribution analysis, Section 6.3 the resource analysis, Section 6.4 the duration analysis, Section 6.5 the transition analysis, Section 6.6 the cycle analysis, Section 6.7 the model soundness analysis, and Section 6.8 the behavioral footprint analysis.

6.1 Variant Analysis

The merging of events belonging to the same activity instance prevents the inflation of trace variants in the XES event log, as described in Section 4.5. Table 6.1 reports the effect of this merging step on the processed dataset.

Dataset	Type	Distinct variants	Total cases
Processed	XES event log	62	5228
	Merged XES event log	23	5228

Table 6.1: Distinct trace variant counts in the XES event logs before and after merging

While the total number of cases remains unchanged, the number of distinct trace variants is substantially reduced for both datasets, indicating that merging contributes to a more representative and less fragmented view of the process behavior.

Table 6.2 shows the merged XES event logs trace variants of the processed dataset, including the number of times the trace appeared before and after the merging.

ID	Trace	Cases Before	%	Cases After	%
1	Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	2738	52.4%	2824	54.0%
2	Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	782	15.0%	788	15.1%
3	Start work process, Assessment, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	139	2.7%	873	16.7%
4	Start work process, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	38	0.7%	349	6.7%
5	Start work process, Assessment, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	155	3.0%	259	5.0%
6	Start work process, End work process	50	1.0%	50	1.0%
7	Start work process, Consultant handling, End work process	37	0.7%	37	0.7%
8	Start work process, Requesting information, Waiting for information - 1, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	14	0.3%	19	0.4%
9	Start work process, Administrative handling, End work process	2	0.0%	4	0.1%
10	Assessment, Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	1	0.0%	2	0.0%
11	Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, Investigation, Administrative handling, End work process	0	0.0%	2	0.0%
12	Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, Investigation, End work process	0	0.0%	2	0.0%
13	Start work process, Requesting information, Waiting for information - 1, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	3	0.1%	7	0.1%
14	Start work process, Assessment, Administrative handling, End work process	0	0.0%	1	0.0%
15	Assessment, Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	1	0.0%	1	0.0%
16	Start work process, Assessment, Requesting information, Waiting for information - 1, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	1	0.0%	1	0.0%
17	Start work process, Assessment, Requesting information, Waiting for information - 1, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	1	0.0%	1	0.0%
18	Start work process, Waiting for information - 2, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	1	0.0%	1	0.0%
19	Start work process, Consultant handling, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	0	0.0%	1	0.0%
20	Start work process, Consultant handling, Consultant handling, End work process	0	0.0%	1	0.0%
21	Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, Consultant handling, End work process	1	0.0%	1	0.0%
22	Start work process, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	0	0.0%	1	0.0%
23	Start work process, Assessment, Investigation, Administrative handling, Consultant handling, End work process	0	0.0%	1	0.0%
	Total	3964	75.85 %	5228	100 %

Table 6.2: Frequencies of trace variants in the processed XES event log.

The distribution of trace variants shows that the most dominant variant remains unchanged after merging. At the same time, several variants that previously accounted for only a small fraction of cases become more prominent after the merging of the activity instances. Notably, the third most frequent variant before merging becomes the second most frequent afterwards. This indicates that these variants are in fact more representative of the underlying process than they appeared before merging. While a number of infrequent variants remain, their overall impact is limited. Overall, the merging step reduces variant fragmentation and produces a clearer and more representative set of trace variants, indicating that the merging step achieved its intended effect.

The descriptive model is discovered using a noise threshold, which serves to filter out infrequent behavior from the XES event log to produce a simpler process model. As a result, not all trace variants are retained in the discovered model.

Table 6.3 presents the variants from the merged XES event log that conform to the discovered process model, while Table 6.4 lists the variants that are excluded by this filtering step.

These tables show that the noise threshold does not simply filter out all infrequent traces while retaining only the dominant traces. Instead, it removes traces that structurally diverge from the main process behavior, even if they occur relatively often (e.g., ID 4 with 349 cases). At the same time, some low frequency traces are still retained, as they align structurally with the more dominant traces. In this way, the descriptive model preserves both the most frequent variants and structurally consistent but less frequent ones, while filtering out deviant behavior.

The normative model is generated from the regulatory patterns, which represent the intended workflow of the municipality. The trace variants in the merged XES event log capture the actual observed behavior of the process, and comparing the two makes it possible to assess whether the process execution conforms to the intended workflow or deviates from it.

Table 6.5 lists the trace variants that are fully conformant with the normative model, while Table 6.6 lists the variants that deviate from it and thus represent violations of the intended process.

These tables highlight clear differences between the normative and descriptive models, as several high-frequency traces are conformant with the descriptive model but violate the normative model, indicating that while these behaviors are common and structurally consistent with the process, they diverge from the municipality's intended regulatory workflow. This points to a structural gap between how the process is designed and how it is actually executed.

This section covered the different variant analyses that are performed. The next section covers the event analysis.

ID	Trace	Cases
1	Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	2824
2	Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	788
3	Start work process, Assessment, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	873
5	Start work process, Assessment, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	259
8	Start work process, Requesting information, Waiting for information - 1, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	19
10	Assessment, Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	2
13	Start work process, Requesting information, Waiting for information - 1, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	7
15	Assessment, Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	1
16	Start work process, Assessment, Requesting information, Waiting for information - 1, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	1
17	Start work process, Assessment, Requesting information, Waiting for information - 1, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	1
18	Start work process, Waiting for information - 2, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	1
21	Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, Consultant handling, End work process	1
	Total	4779

Table 6.3: Retained trace variants in the descriptive model.

ID	Trace	Cases
4	Start work process, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	349
6	Start work process, End work process	50
7	Start work process, Consultant handling, End work process	37
9	Start work process, Administrative handling, End work process	4
11	Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, Investigation, Administrative handling, End work process	2
12	Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, Investigation, End work process	2
14	Start work process, Assessment, Administrative handling, End work process	1
19	Start work process, Consultant handling, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	1
20	Start work process, Consultant handling, Consultant handling, End work process	1
22	Start work process, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	1
23	Start work process, Assessment, Investigation, Administrative handling, Consultant handling, End work process	1
	Total	449

Table 6.4: Excluded trace variants in the descriptive model.

ID	Trace	Cases
3	Start work process, Assessment, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	873
5	Start work process, Assessment, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	259
16	Start work process, Assessment, Requesting information, Waiting for information - 1, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	1
17	Start work process, Assessment, Requesting information, Waiting for information - 1, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	1
	Total	1134

Table 6.5: Conformant trace variants in the normative model.

ID	Trace	Cases
1	Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	2824
2	Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	788
4	Start work process, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	349
6	Start work process, End work process	50
7	Start work process, Consultant handling, End work process	37
8	Start work process, Requesting information, Waiting for information - 1, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	19
9	Start work process, Administrative handling, End work process	4
10	Assessment, Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	2
11	Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, Investigation, Administrative handling, End work process	2
12	Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, Investigation, End work process	2
13	Start work process, Requesting information, Waiting for information - 1, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	7
14	Start work process, Assessment, Administrative handling, End work process	1
15	Assessment, Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	1
18	Start work process, Waiting for information - 2, Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, End work process	1
19	Start work process, Consultant handling, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	1
20	Start work process, Consultant handling, Consultant handling, End work process	1
21	Start work process, Investigation, Consultant handling, Consultant handling, End work process	1
22	Start work process, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, Investigation, Consultant handling, End work process	1
23	Start work process, Assessment, Investigation, Administrative handling, Consultant handling, End work process	1
	Total	4094

Table 6.6: Violating trace variants in the normative model.

6.2 Event Analysis

The event analysis begins by examining the start and end events of the cases in the XES event log. These provide insights into how the processes are initiated and concluded. Table 6.7 presents the start and end events along with their frequencies.

Start event	Case count
Start work process	5225
Assessment	3
End event	Case count
End work process	5228

Table 6.7: Start and end events identified in the processed XES event log.

The table shows that a majority of the cases in the processed dataset begin with the artificial starting stage, which is to be expected as they are added as the first event of the cases. Interestingly, *Assessment* also appears as a starting event in a small fraction of cases. This is notable, as the artificial start stages were added with a timestamp equal to the case start time, which should in principle prevent other activities from appearing as initial events. The occurrence of *Assessment* as a start event may therefore point to irregularities in the event recording or to exceptional cases where the assessment stage is registered before the actual start time of the case.

All the cases end with the *End work process* event, which is to be expected, as the preprocessing removed the cases which did not comply with this.

The next event analysis shows the overall frequency distributions of the different events for the XES event log and the merged XES event log, which are shown in Figure 6.1

Figure 6.1: Comparison of event frequencies in the XES event log and the merged XES event log.

The observed differences between the two event logs are caused by the merging of activity instances. In particular, the *Investigation* event is often part of an activity instance consisting of multiple events, which explains its higher frequency in the raw log. Additionally, the figure also highlights that certain events are rarely executed and occur only in a very small number of cases.

The final event analysis examines the overall frequency distribution of the different lifecycle transitions in the XES event log, as shown in Table 6.8.

Lifecycle transition	Count		
complete	25,709	reassign	153
start	1,289	resume	3
terminate	3	suspend	1

Table 6.8: Frequencies of lifecycle transitions in the XES event log.

The results indicate that the majority of recorded events are associated with the *complete* transition, while other transitions occur only rarely. This is consistent with the overall event frequencies shown in Figure 6.1, as the merging of activity instances removes the additional transitions in the merged XES event log.

This section covered the different event analyses that are performed. The next section covers the resource analysis.

6.3 Resource Analysis

The resource analysis focuses on the different resources involved in executing the process, which consist of both employees and teams. These are analyzed separately as well as in combination. This provides insights into how the workload is distributed across the process and how responsibilities are shared within the organization. Figure 6.2 shows the distribution of events across teams.

Figure 6.2: Count of executed events by team ID.

The workload is highly uneven, with some teams responsible for thousands of events while others contribute only marginally. The minimal involvement of certain teams likely reflects their responsibility for events that occur only rarely, as is shown in the event analysis. The *Unknown* team ID is caused by events that lack a recorded team allocation.

Figure 6.3 shows the number of events executed by the different employees. To improve readability, only the fifty most active employees are included, as the process involves a large number of employees who contribute only a small number of events. The complete distribution of all employees is available in the project repository.

Figure 6.3: Count of executed events by top 50 Employee ID.

The figure shows that distribution is very uneven. Although many employees are involved in the process, a relatively small number of them carry out the majority of the events.

Figure 6.4 shows the most frequent combinations of employees and their associated teams. This combined view highlights which individuals dominate within their teams and how responsibility is distributed. It not only reveals which teams are critical, but also which employees within those teams handle the largest share of events. As with the individual teams and employees, the distribution is uneven, which is to be expected since this figure combines the same perspectives.

Figure 6.4: Count of executed events by top 50 Team ID + Employee ID.

This section covered the different resource analyses that are performed. The next section covers the duration analysis.

6.4 Duration Analysis

The duration analysis provides insights into the time perspective of the process by measuring how long cases take from start to completion.

Table 6.9 reports the descriptive statistics for case duration, including the total, median, and mean, as well as the shortest and longest observed durations.

Duration metric	Duration
Total case duration	612.81 years
Median case duration	40.56 days
Average case duration	42.77 days
Shortest case duration	8.21 hours
Longest case duration	1.22 years

Table 6.9: Descriptive statistics of case durations.

Table 6.10 reports the total and median case durations for each trace variant. The variants are identified by their ID, which corresponds to the IDs shown in Table 6.2.

ID	Total duration	Median duration	ID	Total duration	Median duration
1	356.95 years	47.67 days	13	1.02 years	46.67 days
2	84.44 years	36.42 days	14	49.33 days	49.33 days
3	121.06 years	52.61 days	15	50.88 days	50.88 days
4	12.24 years	8.42 days	16	132.49 days	132.49 days
5	28.03 years	30.49 days	17	40.51 days	40.51 days
6	1.96 years	6.53 days	18	2.61 days	2.61 days
7	1.04 years	4.36 days	19	26.53 days	26.53 days
8	3.46 years	65.45 days	20	23.57 days	23.57 days
9	16.89 days	0.96 days	21	23.57 days	23.57 days
10	123.65 days	61.82 days	22	63.39 days	63.39 days
11	85.85 days	42.93 days	23	80.48 days	80.48 days
12	115.17 days	57.67 days			

Table 6.10: Case duration statistics per trace variant (total and median).

Substantial variation exists between the different variants. This demonstrates that structural differences in the execution of cases directly impact the throughput times.

To analyze the distribution of individual case durations, Figure 6.5 presents histograms together with a kernel density estimate (KDE).

Figure 6.5: Distribution of individual case durations shown as multiple histograms with a kernel density estimate (KDE).

The figure highlights that most cases are completed within hundred days, while a smaller portion extends to considerably longer durations. This helps to assess whether the process is characterized by a typical runtime or whether substantial variation exists across cases.

Together, these results show both the overall time required by the process and the differences in duration between cases and variants. Identifying which cases and variants take considerably longer is especially useful for detecting inefficiencies within the process execution.

This section covered the different duration analyses that are performed. The next section covers the transition analysis.

6.5 Transition Analysis

The transition analysis compares the transitions and the connections in the normative and descriptive models. It identifies for each transition what the successors are and compares if the successors are the same in both models. Table 6.11 summarizes the succession relations for each transition in both models, as well as the differences between them.

The table highlights several notable differences between the normative and descriptive models. The most notable difference are the successors of the *Start work process*, as both models have completely different successors for this transition.

The normative successors are based on the regulatory patterns table, where the *Start work process* was added as an artificial starting stage, since the workflows did not contain a clearly defined starting stage. As described in Section 4.1.1, the artificial starting stage was connected to the process stages which had no predecessors, thus being identified as a potential starting stage.

Transition	Normative successors	Descriptive successors	Difference
Administrative handling	End work process	End work process	–
Assessment	Investigation, Requesting information	Investigation, Requesting information, Waiting for information – 2	Waiting for information – 2
Consultant handling	Administrative handling, End work process	Administrative handling, Consultant handling, End work process	Consultant handling
Investigation	Consultant handling, Requesting information	Consultant handling	Requesting information
Requesting information	Waiting for information – 1	Waiting for information – 1	–
Return investigation	Administrative handling	–	Administrative handling
Start work process	Assessment, Return investigation	Investigation, Requesting information, Waiting for information – 2	Assessment, Investigation, Requesting information, Return investigation, Waiting for information – 2
Waiting for information – 1	Investigation, Requesting information, Waiting for information – 2	Investigation	Requesting information, Waiting for information – 2
Waiting for information – 2	Investigation, Waiting for information – 1	Investigation, Requesting information	Requesting information, Waiting for information – 1

Table 6.11: Comparison of successor transitions in the normative and descriptive models.

However, the descriptive model indicates that the actual data in the XES event log has different successors for the artificial starting stage. This mismatch suggests a gap between the regulatory pattern and the practical execution of the process.

Another difference is that the descriptive model has no successors for the *Return investigation* transition, as this transition is absent from the model altogether. This absence may indicate that the event never occurs in the XES event log, or alternatively, that it was filtered out during the discovery process due to its infrequency in the observed behavior.

This section covered the transition analysis that is performed. The next section covers the cycle analysis results.

6.6 Cycle Analysis

The cycle analysis checks whether the normative and descriptive models contain cycles and whether such cycles are actually observed in the XES event log. A cycle is a loop where the model allows a sequence of events to return to an earlier event, potentially repeating.

Table 6.12 shows the cycles in the normative model and the frequency of that cycle observed in the XES event log.

Normative model cycle	Case count
Investigation, Requesting information, Waiting for information - 1, Investigation	3
Requesting information, Waiting for information - 1, Requesting information	0
Investigation, Requesting information, Waiting for information - 1, Waiting for information - 2, Investigation	0
Waiting for information - 1, Waiting for information - 2, Waiting for information - 1	0

Table 6.12: Cycles in the normative model.

The results for the normative model show that although four potential cycles are structurally possible, only one of them occurs in practice, and even then only three times.

Table 6.13 shows the cycles in the descriptive model and the frequency of that cycle observed in the XES event log.

Descriptive model cycle	Case count
Consultant handling, Consultant handling (self-loop)	1

Table 6.13: Cycles in the descriptive model.

The results for the descriptive model show that it contains only a single self-loop, which is observed once in the event log. Since the descriptive model is discovered from the XES event log, it is expected that any cycle present in the model also appears in the log.

There are no cycles that overlap between the normative and descriptive models. However, when analyzing the event log directly, several more cycles can be observed. Table 6.14 shows the cycles in the XES event log and the frequency of cycle.

XES event log cycle	Case count
Consultant handling, Consultant handling	1
Investigation, Consultant handling, Investigation	2
Investigation, Consultant handling, Administrative handling, Investigation	2
Investigation, Requesting information, Waiting for information – 1, Investigation	3
Consultant handling, Administrative handling, Investigation, Consultant handling	1
Consultant handling, Investigation, Consultant handling	1

Table 6.14: Cycles in the XES event log

As these cycles are not represented in the descriptive model, this indicates that they belong to trace variants that were excluded during the discovery of the descriptive process model.

In summary, cycles exist in both the normative and descriptive models and are also present in the XES event log, but they occur only at very low frequencies. This shows that while looping behavior is possible, it is not characteristic of the majority of cases.

This section covered the different cycle analyses that are performed. The next section covers the soundness analysis results.

6.7 Soundness Analysis

The soundness analysis evaluates whether the normative and descriptive process models are behaviorally well formed. A sound Workflow Net should not contain dead transitions, livelocks, or deadlocks, and it should always allow proper completion of cases. Table 6.15 reports the results for both the raw and the processed XES event logs.

Type	Normative model		Descriptive model	
	WF-net	Sound	WF-net	Sound
Raw	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Processed	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Table 6.15: Soundness analysis results for the normative and descriptive models, based on both raw and processed XES event logs.

These results confirm that both the normative and descriptive models are correctly generated, as they are valid workflow nets and behaviorally sound.

This section covered the soundness analysis that is performed. The next section will covers the footprint analysis results.

6.8 Footprint Analysis

The footprint analysis compares the normative and descriptive models by transforming their control-flow relations into footprint matrices and highlighting discrepancies. These relations describe whether two transitions are causally related, can occur in parallel, or are mutually exclusive.

Figures 6.6, 6.7, 6.8, and 6.9 show the footprint matrices of the normative model, descriptive model, and their comparisons, respectively. In these matrices, symbols represent the type of relation between transitions:

- $>$ denotes a causal relation (one transition directly precedes the other),
- \parallel denotes a parallel relation (either order of execution is possible),
- $\#$ denotes an exclusive relation (the transitions never occur in direct succession).

The comparison matrices highlights several mismatches between the normative and descriptive models, which are marked in red. The different mismatches are shown in Table 6.16.

This chapter presented the results of the frameworks process diagnostics in detail, using the selected process from Municipality A as a running example. The next chapter will present the discussion and conclusion of the thesis.

Transitions	Normative relation	Descriptive relation
Return investigation, Administrative handling	Causal (>)	No relation
Start work process, Assessment	Causal (>)	Parallel ()
Start work process, Return investigation	Causal (>)	No relation
Start work process, Investigation	Exclusive (#)	Causal (>)
Start work process, Requesting information	Exclusive (#)	Causal (>)
Start work process, Waiting for information-2	Exclusive (#)	Causal (>)
Investigation, Requesting information	Causal (>)	Exclusive (#)
Requesting information, Waiting for information-1	Parallel ()	Causal (>)
Waiting for information-1, Waiting for information-2	Parallel ()	Exclusive (#)
Waiting for information-2, Requesting information	Exclusive (#)	Causal (>)
Consultant Handling, Consultant Handling	Exclusive (#)	Parallel ()
Assessment, Waiting for information-2	Exclusive (#)	Causal (>)

Table 6.16: Comparison of footprint matrix relations in the normative and descriptive models.

	Administrative handling	Assessment	Consultant handling	End work process	Investigation	Requesting information	Return investigation	Start work process	Waiting for information - 1	Waiting for information - 2
Administrative handling	#	#	<	>	#	#	<	#	#	#
Assessment	#	#	#	#	>	>	#	<	#	#
Consultant handling	>	#	#	>	<	#	#	#	#	#
End work process	<	#	<	#	#	#	#	#	#	#
Investigation	#	<	>	#	#	>	#	#	<	<
Requesting information	#	<	#	#	<	#	#	#		#
Return investigation	>	#	#	#	#	#	#	<	#	#
Start work process	#	>	#	#	#	#	>	#	#	#
Waiting for information - 1	#	#	#	#	>		#	#	#	
Waiting for information - 2	#	#	#	#	>	#	#	#		#

Figure 6.6: Normative model footprint matrix.

	Administrative handling	Assessment	Consultant handling	End work process	Investigation	Requesting information	Start work process	Waiting for information - 1	Waiting for information - 2
Administrative handling	#	#	<	>	#	#	#	#	#
Assessment	#	#	#	#	>	>		#	>
Consultant handling	>	#		>	<	#	#	#	#
End work process	<	#	<	#	#	#	#	#	#
Investigation	#	<	>	#	#	#	<	<	<
Requesting information	#	<	#	#	#	#	<	>	<
Start work process	#		#	#	>	>	#	#	>
Waiting for information - 1	#	#	#	#	>	<	#	#	#
Waiting for information - 2	#	<	#	#	>	>	<	#	#

Figure 6.7: Descriptive model footprint matrix.

	Administrative handling	Assessment	Consultant handling	End work process	Investigation	Requesting information	Return investigation	Start work process	Waiting for information - 1	Waiting for information - 2
Administrative handling	#	#	<	>	#	#	<	#	#	#
Assessment	#	#	#	#	>	>	#	<	#	#
Consultant handling	>	#	#	>	<	#	#	#	#	#
End work process	<	#	<	#	#	#	#	#	#	#
Investigation	#	<	>	#	#	>	#	#	<	<
Requesting information	#	<	#	#	<	#	#	#		#
Return investigation	>	#	#	#	#	#	#	<	#	#
Start work process	#	>	#	#	#	#	>	#	#	#
Waiting for information - 1	#	#	#	#	>		#	#	#	
Waiting for information - 2	#	#	#	#	>	#	#	#		#

Figure 6.8: Comparison of the normative footprint matrix with the descriptive model.

	Administrative handling	Assessment	Consultant handling	End work process	Investigation	Requesting information	Start work process	Waiting for information - 1	Waiting for information - 2
Administrative handling	#	#	<	>	#	#	#	#	#
Assessment	#	#	#	#	>	>		#	>
Consultant handling	>	#		>	<	#	#	#	#
End work process	<	#	<	#	#	#	#	#	#
Investigation	#	<	>	#	#	#	<	<	<
Requesting information	#	<	#	#	#	#	<	>	<
Start work process	#		#	#	>	>	#	#	>
Waiting for information - 1	#	#	#	#	>	<	#	#	#
Waiting for information - 2	#	<	#	#	>	>	<	#	#

Figure 6.9: Comparison of the descriptive footprint matrix with the normative model.

7 Discussion and Conclusion

This chapter presents the discussion and conclusion of the thesis. The chapter is structured as follows:

Section 7.1 discusses the practical and research implications, outlines the limitations and threats to validity, and indicates directions for future work. Section 7.2 concludes the thesis by answering the main research question and the sub-questions directly.

7.1 Discussion

This section discusses practical and research implications of the designed framework, the diagnostic results presented in Chapter 6, the limitations and threats to validity of this thesis, and indicates directions for future work.

The framework designed in this thesis provides an end-to-end pipeline that extracts raw municipal process data and transforms it into an XES event log, a normative model of the intended behavior, and a descriptive model of the actual behavior. It then applies process diagnostics to these outputs to derive insights. The section is structured as follows:

Section 7.1.1 discusses the practical implications, Section 7.1.2 discusses the research implications, Section 7.1.3 discusses the limitations and threats to validity, and Section 7.1.4 discusses directions for future work.

7.1.1 Practical Implications

The framework provides municipalities with a reproducible way to turn their raw process data into process diagnostic results that offer insights into various aspects of the process.

As Chapter 6 illustrates for one process in the Municipality A case study, the diagnostics provide a coherent overview to: (i) compare intended and actual behavior, (ii) assess throughput times, (iii) examine workload distribution across resources, (iv) summarize the distribution of executed events, and (v) identify the most common trace variants.

Municipalities can translate the resulting insights, detected deviations, and process knowledge into potential improvements. This thesis and the designed framework do not aim to prescribe actionable improvements. Instead, they aim to provide the tools and analyses needed for municipalities to identify and implement them.

Additionally, the framework stores all the intermediate outputs, including the XES event logs and the normative and descriptive models, in standard formats (e.g., XES, PNML, BPMN). Beyond the diagnostics produced by the framework, this enables municipalities to load these intermediate outputs into other process-mining tools to obtain additional insights and integrate it with their existing reporting systems.

Thus far, some practical implications of the thesis have been discussed. However, the outcome of this work also informs research in process mining, as the next subsection illustrates.

7.1.2 Research Implications

The framework's design and implementation are public, transparent, and reproducible, except for the database extraction step, which cannot be shared due to privacy constraints. Each step is documented in detail with clear pseudo code and data-structure overviews, and both intermediate and final outputs are stored in standard formats (XES, PNML/BPMN). Although the implementation targets municipal data, the transparency and documentation provide a template that can be adapted to other domains.

The designed framework shows that both the XES event logs and the normative models can be built directly from raw municipal process data with domain knowledge, instead of being assumed or created solely with expert input. The preprocessing and event-log construction make explicit how the different tables are combined, how data quality issues are addressed, and how lifecycle semantics are added. The normative models are generated in a systematic and reproducible way from regulatory patterns derived from the same data and documentation. This enables full traceability and reproducibility of the process mining and diagnostic procedures, from raw data to the final results that can inform future research in this area. In fact, the outcome of this thesis is in line with the objectives of the international research project *Explainable Knowledge-aware Process Intelligence* (PINPOINT)¹.

For the case studies, the raw data, intermediate steps, and outputs are made publicly available, so other researchers can work with real-world municipal datasets. Specifically, the output of this thesis is being used as a test bench and real-world use case for the enhancement of the Sp3lls Wizard technique by Barbaro et al. [46].

In addition to its practical and research implications, this thesis is subject to certain limitations and threats to validity, which are addressed in the next subsection.

7.1.3 Limitations and Threats to Validity

There are several limitations and threats to validity:

Start times of cases and events are stored as dates, without a time-of-day. This limits duration analysis, as exact execution time cannot be derived. Additionally, event order within a case is therefore inferred from end timestamps. In practice, it should not be possible for two events, within the same case, to be in active execution at the same time. However, this cannot be guaranteed or verified from the data.

Municipalities specify intended workflows using only exclusive choices and, by extension, the regulatory table models exclusive paths only. The normative model generation is therefore limited to contain no concurrency.

¹<https://pinpoint.unibz.it/>

When an intended workflow lacks an explicit start, preprocessing introduces an artificial start stage and connects it to all potential start stages (i.e., stages with no predecessors in the regulatory patterns). It could be that some stages with predecessors were also intended as alternative starts by the municipality, but this cannot be derived from the process data.

Preprocessing removed cases with invalid end dates, undefined process stages, or missing closing stages. These are data-quality issues, due to unknown reasons in the underlying reporting system. Removing them improves consistency, but it also changes the distribution of traces and may filter out rare behavior.

The discovered descriptive models depend on the discovery configuration, which uses the Inductive Miner (infrequent) with an empirically selected noise threshold. Because the miner and threshold influence model structure and reported metrics, alternative configurations could produce different outcomes, which were not systematically evaluated.

The framework was tested on two municipal datasets, both provided by Centric. Although Centric delivers standardized software solutions, municipalities retain freedom to configure their own processes and workflows. As a result, certain preprocessing steps and model-construction procedures in the framework may require adaptation to municipality-specific configurations. Therefore, it cannot be claimed that the framework is fully generalized across all municipalities that are connected to Centric, and its applicability may vary depending on local configurations.

The limitations and threats to validity have been analyzed from a technical perspective, the next subsection addresses limitations that indicate directions for future research.

7.1.4 Future Work

There are several potential directions for future work.

The first is to apply the framework's design to process data from other domains. This would test whether the preprocessing steps and the construction of the XES event log and the normative models can be generalized into a less domain-specific approach, and what adaptations are needed.

The second is to enable benchmarking between municipalities by running the framework on comparable processes. Comparing the normative models and the XES event logs across municipalities could provide additional insights, support evaluation of efficiency, and highlight concrete opportunities for improvement for lower-scoring municipalities.

The third is to extend the normative model derivation with concurrency. The municipal regulatory patterns from this thesis do not specify whether activities must be executed exclusively or in parallel and as a result, the generated normative models exclude concurrency. If the patterns are extended to indicate where parallelism is permitted, the normative model generation could be extended to include explicit parallel and exclusive branching, making the systematic creation of normative models more expressive in domains where concurrency is present.

The fourth is to extend the validation beyond the Centric ecosystem. While this thesis focused on municipalities using Centric's software solutions, other municipalities operate on different vendor systems with distinct data structures and regulatory configurations. Applying the framework in such environments would test its adaptability to alternative ecosystems and configurations.

Finally, the results will be presented to the involved stakeholders to gather their feedback and validate the provided insights. This step is not documented here, as the workshop with stakeholders is scheduled to take place after the presentation of this thesis.

This section discussed the practical and research implications, as well as the limitations and threats to validity, and the future work directions. The next chapter will conclude the thesis by answering the main research question and the sub-questions.

7.2 Conclusion

This section answers the three sub-research questions and the main research question, and reflects on the findings and contributions of this thesis.

SRQ1. *What are the characteristics and challenges of raw municipal process data in the social domain, and how can it be effectively processed and restructured for process mining?*

The raw municipal process data is characterized by its fragmentation across multiple database tables and its inherently multi-process perspective. These tables consist of various domain-specific mandatory attributes, which are essential for identifying processes and tracking the state of individual cases. A domain-specific process identifier, defined by the combination of the mandatory attributes *LawId*, *ProcessCategory*, and *ProcessSubCategory*, distinguishes the different processes within the raw process data. Municipalities apply several distinct laws, which are divided into categories, and these in turn may contain subcategories that specify the nature of an application. In addition to execution data, the raw process data also records the intended workflows of the processes.

Although municipalities generate large volumes of such process data, it is not directly suitable for process mining and therefore often remains unused. The framework designed in this thesis introduces systematic preprocessing to resolve data-quality issues and transforms the fragmented tables into structured XES event logs that capture actual execution behavior, and regulatory patterns that capture the intended workflows for each process identifier. This results in separate data for each distinct process.

This approach demonstrates that, despite the raw data's characteristics of being unstructured, fragmented, and inherently multi-process, as well as the presence of various data-quality challenges, municipal process data can be effectively processed and restructured into inputs for process mining, enabling the systematic analysis of various processes.

SRQ2. *How can descriptive and normative process models be systematically generated to enable the analysis of municipal processes?*

Descriptive models are systematically discovered from the generated XES event logs using the Inductive Miner in combination with a noise threshold. To ensure accuracy, events belonging to

the same activity instance are merged before discovery, preventing inflated trace variants caused by duplicate event records. The noise threshold is empirically determined by evaluating a range of values against fitness, precision, simplicity, and generalization metrics, achieving a balanced trade-off between model quality dimensions.

Normative models are systematically generated directly from the regulatory pattern data, which capture the intended workflows defined by the municipality. These patterns specify, for each event in the process, the possible successor events, providing a structured and reproducible foundation for deriving normative process models.

By integrating these two approaches, the framework delivers both descriptive and normative models in a systematic, transparent, and reproducible manner. This enables municipalities to directly compare actual execution behavior with the intended process behavior.

SRQ3. *What insights and deviations can be derived from analyzing and comparing process models to support potential improvement of municipal processes?*

The framework's process diagnostics enable systematic comparison of descriptive and normative models, revealing concrete deviations between intended and actual behavior. The key analyses include: (i) *Variant analysis*, which compares trace variants in the XES event log to assess whether they conform to either model; (ii) *Transition analysis*, which examines, for each event, the successor events in both models and highlights structural differences in the control-flow; (iii) *Cycle analysis*, which investigates whether cycles are present in both models and whether they align; and (iv) *Footprint analysis*, which compares the relations between transitions across the models, identifying discrepancies.

In addition, diagnostics such as the *duration analysis*, *event analysis*, and *resource analysis* provided insights into process efficiency and performance. These revealed where bottlenecks occurred, how long processes took to complete, and how workloads were distributed among resources. Collectively, these analyses made inefficiencies, deviations, and performance issues visible in a systematic and interpretable manner.

Overall, these insights and deviations form a basis for municipalities to evaluate and potentially improve their processes, while leaving the concrete improvement decisions to the municipalities themselves.

RQ. *How can process knowledge be extracted from raw municipal process data to enable the analysis and (potential) improvement of municipal processes in the social domain via process mining?*

This thesis has shown that process knowledge can be systematically extracted from raw municipal process data by designing and applying a structured, end-to-end framework. The framework first preprocesses and restructures fragmented and noisy municipal data into standardized XES event logs and regulatory patterns for each process (SRQ1). From these, it systematically generates descriptive models that capture the actual execution behavior and normative models that represent the intended workflows defined by municipalities (SRQ2). By applying conformance checking and other process diagnostics, the framework then shows the deviations between actual and intended

behavior and the performance characteristics of the processes, such as throughput times, workload distribution, and bottlenecks (SRQ3).

Together, the steps of the framework translate raw municipal process data into concrete insights on process behavior and performance within the social domain. The framework does not prescribe specific improvements, but instead provides municipalities with a reproducible and interpretable set of analyses to evaluate compliance, identify inefficiencies, and assess opportunities for improvement.

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A Ethics and Privacy Quick Scan

Response Summary:

Section 1. Research projects involving human participants

P1. Does your project involve human participants? This includes for example use of observation, (online) surveys, interviews, tests, focus groups, and workshops where human participants provide information or data to inform the research. If you are only using existing data sets or publicly available data (e.g. from X, Reddit) without directly recruiting participants, please answer no.

- Yes

Recruitment

P2. Does your project involve participants younger than 16 years of age?

- No

P3. Does your project involve participants with learning or communication difficulties of a severity that may impact their ability to provide informed consent?

- No

P4. Is your project likely to involve participants engaging in illegal activities?

- No

P5. Does your project involve patients?

- No

P6. Does your project involve participants belonging to a vulnerable group, other than those listed above?

- No

P8. Does your project involve participants with whom you have, or are likely to have, a working or professional relationship: for instance, staff or students of the university, professional colleagues, or clients?

- Yes

P9. Is it made clear to potential participants that not participating will in no way impact them (e.g. it will not directly impact their grade in a class)?

- Yes

Informed consent

PC1. Do you have set procedures that you will use for obtaining informed consent prior to collecting data from all participants, including (where appropriate) parental consent for children or consent from legally authorized representatives? (See suggestions for information sheets and consent forms on [the website](#).)

- Yes

PC2. Will you tell participants that their participation is voluntary?

- Yes

PC3. Will you obtain explicit consent for participation?

- Yes

PC4. Will you obtain explicit consent for any sensor readings, eye tracking, photos, audio, and/or video recordings?

- Not applicable

PC5. Will you tell participants that they may withdraw from the research at any time and for any reason?

- Yes

PC6. Will you give potential participants time to consider participation?

- Yes

PC7. Will you provide participants with an opportunity to ask questions about the research before consenting to take part (e.g. by providing your contact details)?

- Yes

PC8. Does your project involve concealment or deliberate misleading of participants?

- No

Section 2. Data protection, handling, and storage

The General Data Protection Regulation imposes several obligations for the use of **personal data** (defined as any information relating to an identified or identifiable living person) or including the use of personal data in research.

D1. Are you gathering or using personal data (defined as any information relating to an identified or identifiable living person)?

- No

Section 3. Research that may cause harm

Research may cause harm to participants, researchers, the university, or society. This includes when technology has dual-use, and you investigate an innocent use, but your results could be used by others in a harmful way. If you are unsure regarding possible harm to the university or society, please discuss your concerns with the Research Support Office.

H1. Does your project give rise to a realistic risk to the national security of any country?

- No

H2. Does your project give rise to a realistic risk of aiding human rights abuses in any country?

- No

H3. Does your project (and its data) give rise to a realistic risk of damaging the University's reputation? (E.g., bad press coverage, public protest.)

- No

H4. Does your project (and in particular its data) give rise to an increased risk of attack (cyber- or otherwise) against the University? (E.g., from pressure groups.)

- No

H5. Is the data likely to contain material that is indecent, offensive, defamatory, threatening, discriminatory, or extremist?

- No

H6. Does your project give rise to a realistic risk of harm to the researchers?

- No

H7. Is there a realistic risk of any participant experiencing physical or psychological harm or discomfort?

- No

H8. Is there a realistic risk of any participant experiencing a detriment to their interests as a result of participation?

- No

H9. Is there a realistic risk of other types of negative externalities?

- No

Section 4. Conflicts of interest

C1. Is there any potential conflict of interest (e.g. between research funder and researchers or participants and researchers) that may potentially affect the research outcome or the dissemination of research findings?

- No

C2. Is there a direct hierarchical relationship between researchers and participants?

- No

Section 5. Your information.

This last section collects data about you and your project so that we can register that you completed the Ethics and Privacy Quick Scan, sent you (and your supervisor/course coordinator) a summary of what you filled out, and follow up where a fuller ethics review and/or privacy assessment is needed. For details of our legal basis for using personal data and the rights you have over your data please see the [University's privacy information](#). Please see the guidance on the [ICS Ethics and Privacy website](#) on what happens on submission.

Z0. Which is your main department?

- Information and Computing Science

Z1. Your full name:

Floris van Voorst tot Voorst

Z2. Your email address:

F.C.vanvoorsttotvoorst@students.uu.nl

Z3. In what context will you conduct this research?

- As a student for my master thesis, supervised by:
Dr. C. Di Ciccio

Z5. Master programme for which you are doing the thesis

- Computing Science

Z6. Email of the course coordinator or supervisor (so that we can inform them that you filled this out and provide them with a summary):

c.diccio@uu.nl

Z7. Email of the moderator (as provided by the coordinator of your thesis project):

coordinator.cosc@uu.nl

Z8. Title of the research project/study for which you filled out this Quick Scan:

Analyzing Municipal Event Data with Process Mining: A Multi-Layered Visualization Approach

Z9. Summary of what you intend to investigate and how you will investigate this (200 words max):

This research explores how combining process mining with a multi-layered visualization framework can improve the analysis and optimization of municipal processes within the social domain. While municipalities share similar processes, each implements them differently. Integrating process mining with benchmarking and a visualization offers potential improvements in these processes. The main research question is:

How can a multi-layered visualization framework aid in analyzing, benchmarking, and improving municipal processes in the social domain via process mining?

To answer this, three sub-questions are formulated:

SRQ1: What types of data are generated by municipal processes, and how can they be structured for process mining?

This question focuses on identifying and structuring municipal data for analysis, considering factors like data availability, process complexity, and relevance.

SRQ2: How can process mining techniques be applied to analyze municipal event data and benchmark social domain processes?

This question explores the application of process mining to identify inefficiencies and benchmark processes for improvement.

SRQ3: How can the backdrop and layers of the visualization be designed to provide context, guidance, and cues for improving municipal processes?

This sub-question investigates the design of a multi-layered visualization to enhance understanding and decision-making for stakeholders.

Z10. In case you encountered warnings in the survey, does supervisor already have ethical approval for a research line that fully covers your project?

- Not applicable

Scoring

- Privacy: 0
 - Ethics: 0
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